

Needs & gaps within and across regions and the associated local contexts

D2.1

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TABLE 1: DOCUMENT INFORMATION

¹ PU = public | PP = Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services) | RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services) | CO= Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

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TABLE 2: DOCUMENT HISTORY

Abbreviations

IPM	INTEGRATED PEST MANAGEMENT	ADAS	AGRICULTURAL DEVELOPMENT AND ADVISORY SERVICE
IWM	INTEGRATED WEED MANAGEMENT	LEAF	LINKING ENVIRONMENT AND FARMING
AKIS	AGRICULTURAL KNOWLEDGE AND INNOVATION SYSTEMS	AHDB	AGRICULTURE AND HORTICULTURE DEVELOPMENT BOARD
NN	NATIONAL NETWORK	NNO	NATIONAL NETWORK OPERATOR
NAP	NATIONAL ACTION PLAN	GHG	GREEN HOUSE GAS
SFI	SUSTAINABLE FARMING INCENTIVE		

TABLE 3: ABBREVIATIONS

Participants

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Document summary

A stakeholder survey was completed within each project country to identify the needs and barriers for alternative weed control uptake. In this context, needs are defined as actions required to increase uptake of alternative weed control. Barriers are defined as the socio-economic, political, regulatory, biophysical and technological gaps that may prevent farmers from increasing their uptake of alternative weed control solutions. Following these results, a focus group meeting was held by each project partner with experts of weed management in different sectors and management styles within each country. These experts provided contextual insight into the results of the online survey and further expanded on the main needs, gaps and barriers for alternative weed control within a local context.

Executive Summary

This deliverable provides results following the completion of Task 2.1 – Capturing grassroots needs, gaps and associated barriers. The needs & barriers across regions were gathered through the completion of an online survey. The needs and barriers within regions (a local context) were gathered by focus group meetings coordinated within each partner country, providing an opportunity for different stakeholders to contribute additional context to the online survey results. By gathering this information, this deliverable provides essential information for the development of Nation Action Plans (D2.4).

Document content

Part. 1 Introduction

The OPER8 project aims to connect farmers, advisors, researchers and industry representatives within a thematic network across Europe in order to share alternative weed control solutions and increase knowledge exchange between core AKIS (Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems) actors. As such, contact was initiated with key stakeholders from the beginning of the project and developed a National Network (NN) of experts within each country as part of WP1 (T1.1). To identify the potential for farmers to take up alternative weed control methods and the factors that may hinder this, an online survey was conducted to establish what farmers and associated stakeholders require in order to transition to greater uptake of alternative weed control solutions, and current resource gaps across the industry, drawing on contacts within and outside of the NN to disseminate the survey as widely as possible. From this, a series of barriers to uptake of alternative weed control across Europe and the UK were identified. The results of each survey completed within each partner country were discussed with each native NN to gain a deeper insight and contextual understanding behind the results. The data collected from the survey and focus groups will support the development of National Action Plans (NAP), matching the needs of stakeholder across and within each region with technical solutions identified in T2.2 in order to develop Best Practices for alternative weed control for different countries, contexts and farmer profiles (T3.4).

The results identify opportunities for targeted communication and dissemination efforts as well as identifying groups which may require further outreach to increase adoption of alternative weed control. By understanding the barriers to adoption of alternative weed control methods, researchers and practitioners can develop targeted strategies to overcome these barriers and promote more sustainable weed control practices.

This report summarises the results from the surveys and focus groups completed within seven countries in OPER8.

Part. 2 Capturing grassroots needs and barriers: stakeholder surveys.

2.1 Survey methods

The survey was conducted online, targeting farmers, advisors, researchers, and industry representatives. Farmers were asked about their current weed control practices, their knowledge and awareness of alternative methods, and the factors that influence their decision to use or not use these methods. Additionally, participants were asked to identify the challenges they face in adopting alternative weed control methods and the support they need to overcome these challenges.

The survey was hosted by Online Surveys² and was available for participants to complete for approximately two months in 2023. The survey was promoted in each of the seven countries involved in the OPER8 project (Greece, Spain, Italy, Latvia, UK, Sweden, and France) and was available in seven native languages. The survey questions were composed in English and translated to each language ensuring each question remained the same or as similar as possible. The questions within the survey were mostly closed and provided multiple choice options, though there were some open-ended questions also included. All questions from the survey can be found in Appendix 1.

Participants were asked about their primary occupation and their country of residence. The participants could broadly be categorised into two groups: farmers and non-farmers. Participants within each of these groups were asked different questions.

Farmers were asked about the characteristics of their farm, including size, predominant crop type, weed management approach and current weed issues. Farmers were then asked what weed control methods they were using currently through a multiple-choice question and asked to choose the main disadvantage to their current approaches. Disadvantages were provided from a drop-down

² <https://www.onlinesurveys.ac.uk/>

list. Following this, farmers were asked to select weed control methods and strategies that they were interested in but had never used and to state the main barrier preventing the usage of this approach. Farmers were also asked to identify weed control methods which they had used before, but are no longer using, and identify the reason why they were no longer using this approach.

Non-farmers were asked to identify their main occupation and state whether they had direct contact with farmers as part of their professional responsibilities. In addition, non-farmers were asked whether they agreed or disagreed with various statements in relation to both herbicide-based weed control and alternative methods of weed control.

Farmers and non-farmers were asked to what extent they agreed with suggested barriers for uptake of alternative weed control methods. They were also asked to indicate how useful several research or extension priorities were to improve future weed management practices. All Participants were asked to select to what extent they agreed or disagreed with several polarising statements relating to the use of herbicides and their impact on the environment. Finally, characteristics of participants were gathered by asking the age, level of education, length of time working in agriculture and identifying whether participants were involved in any non-governmental agricultural organisations.

A total of 625 valid responses were returned across the seven countries in the European wide stakeholder needs, gaps and barriers for alternative weed control survey in 2023. Participants were categorised as farmers and non-farmers based their responses (Appendix 1: Q3). Out of the 625 responses, 57% were farmers and 43% were non farmers (see Table 5).

TABLE 5. THE NUMBER OF SURVEY PARTICIPANTS CATEGORISED BY THEIR MAIN OCCUPATION AND COUNTRY OF RESIDENCE.

Participant occupation	Country							Total
	France	Spain	Greece	Sweden	Latvia	Italy	UK	
Farmer	67	31	64	27	91	37	44	361
Non-farmer	37	49	28	24	20	40	66	264
Total	104	80	92	51	111	77	110	625

Data were imported to R (R Core Team 2016)³ to allow the data to be grouped and summarised and the results interpreted based on raw data counts for most of the questions.

2.2 Focus group methods

Following the results of the survey, focus group workshops were conducted within each country, led by the National Network Organiser (T2.1). Each focus group required a minimum of 10 participants covering as wide representation of the key stakeholders for weed management (e.g., farmers, advisors, policy makers etc.). The aim of the workshop was to establish the context surrounding survey results and to identify specific needs and barriers for different cropping systems within each country. Discussions on key aspects of the survey results took place and further insight was noted by the focus group coordinators. Focus groups were conducted either in person or online. The dates of each group meeting and number of attendees are shown in Table 6.

TABLE 6. FOCUS GROUP DATE AND TOTAL ATTENDANCE FOR EACH COUNTRY

	Country						
	France	Spain	Greece	Sweden	Latvia	Italy	UK
Date (2023)	13 May	28 July	14 July	17 August	11 July	Sept*	13 July
Attendance	10	16	10	16	13	12	13

*Group was delayed due to farming commitments.

³ R Core Team (2016) R: A language and environment for statistical computing. R Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria. <https://www.r-project.org>. Accessed: February 3, 2017 [Google Scholar](#)

2.3 General needs and barriers across regions; feedback from surveys and focus groups

An important aspect of the focus groups was to delve into the specific needs and barriers for increasing the use of alternative weed control methods within each region involved in OPER8. These needs and barriers are described in the seven country specific reports in Part 3 of this report. Within each focus group, representation of a range of stakeholders was achieved by all National Network Operators (NNOs).

The focus group workshop in Italy was organised too late to be incorporated into this report, but the results of the Italian survey were expanded upon by experts involved in the project.

A key outcome from all focus group meetings was the high dependency on synthetic chemical herbicides that farmers have across regions in the variety of cropping sectors included. In Greece, herbicide use can be influenced by its varied climate, including Mediterranean and temperate regions. Agriculture is an important sector, with olives, fruits, vegetables, and cereals being significant crops. Therefore, technical alternative weed control methods might focus on weed management in olive groves and vineyards, along with other crops. Italy has diverse agricultural landscapes, including cereals and oilseeds, vineyards and olive orchards. Herbicide use may differ based on regions and crops, with high consistency of management required in higher value crops. France is also a major agricultural producer with diverse regions specializing in various crops, including wheat, corn, grapes, and more. With 96% of survey respondents indicating that vineyards were their main crop in France, the needs and barriers addressed in focus group discussions were in-depth and technical for this sector.

Sweden's herbicide reliance was lower compared to other countries according to survey results. This may be partly due to its higher proportion of organic agricultural production. The colder climate and shorter growing seasons might impact the types and amounts of herbicides used. IPM and alternative weed control methods could be more prevalent, despite being legally required by all countries to some extent. Similarly, Latvia's colder climate and diverse crop production could influence its choice of alternative weed control methods. Cereal crops, vegetables, and rapeseed are important. The UK's alternative weed control use can vary based on the type of agriculture practiced, ranging from arable farming to horticulture. Concerns about environmental impact and sustainability might influence herbicide choices and given the growing interest in sustainable agriculture, agroecological approaches and integrated strategies are increasingly prevalent.

Within each country, stakeholders are aware of alternative approaches to weed management and would like to increase their usage due to environmental, ecological and resistance management concerns. But there are several barriers preventing this uptake. Stakeholders discussed priorities needed in place in order to address these barriers within each focus group. To a certain extent, all proposed solutions to increase alternative weed control were applicable to all countries as shown in the online survey results (refer to Q14 & 22, Appendix 1). However, particular needs were discussed in detail by each focus group and were identified as priorities within each country. These priority results are summarised in Table 7. From these discussions, the main priority for increasing the uptake of alternative weed control across regions was through the demonstration of alternative approaches, providing opportunities to stakeholders to access alternative equipment and facilitate peer to peer learning and knowledge exchange. In addition to this, consultations with specialists, trials of alternative methods and subsidies for environmentally friendly farming were also highlighted as priorities across the countries involved in discussion. It was noted that farmers lacked confidence in alternative weed control methods and that this could be improved through increased availability of information.

TABLE 7. SUMMARY OF **PRIORITY NEEDS** FOR UPTAKE OF ALTERNATIVE WEED CONTROL METHODS ACROSS EUROPE FROM THE FOCUS GROUP DISCUSSIONS.

Country	Demonstration events of the methods	Subsidies for environmentally friendly farming	Trials of alternative methods	Recommendations from other farmers	Consultations with a specialist/ experienced user	Greater confidence in the efficacy of alternatives	Grants for the purchase of equipment	Increased availability of information	Public opinion in favour of “greener” methods	Grants for trials
United Kingdom	✓	✓	✓			✓	✓			✓
France	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓			
Italy	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓		✓	✓
Greece	✓	✓		✓	✓		✓	✓	✓	
Latvia	✓		✓		✓	✓	✓	✓		
Sweden	✓		✓	✓	✓	✓				
Spain		✓		✓	✓	✓		✓		
Total	6	5	5	5	5	5	5	3	2	2

✓ indicates the **priority needs** for uptake of alternative weed control. The full list of needs identified are discussed in detail within each specific country section.

Again, all barriers queried in the online survey were, to some extent, indicated as a concern for farmers and non-farmers to increase the use of alternative weed control methods (refer to Q13 & 18, Appendix 1). However, the main barriers identified across regions discussed in detail within focus groups are in Table 8.

TABLE 8. SUMMARY OF THE **MAIN BARRIERS** FOR THE UPTAKE OF ALTERNATIVE WEED CONTROL METHODS ACROSS EUROPE DISCUSSED IN THE FOCUS GROUP WORKSHOP FOR EACH REPRESENTATIVE COUNTRY.

Country	Expense of alternative methods	No access to equipment	Lack of information available	Low efficacy of alternative methods	No opportunities to test alternative methods before investing	Not knowing anyone who uses alternative methods	Alternative methods are time consuming	No skilled advisors are available	Alternative approaches are complicated	Negative effect on Biodiversity of alternative methods
United Kingdom	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓			
France	✓	✓			✓		✓		✓	✓
Italy	✓		✓	✓		✓		✓		
Greece	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓		
Latvia	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓			
Sweden	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓				
Spain	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓					
Total	7	6	6	6	5	3	3	2	1	1

These barriers can be summarised into the following categories:

- **Economic Concerns:** Sustainable alternatives might require initial investment in equipment, training, or changes in practices. Farmers are concerned about the upfront costs and potential impacts on their profitability. Farmers would like to try different weed control methods to increase their confidence before making a substantial investment.
- **Technical Challenges:** Some sustainable alternatives might require specific equipment, skills, or labour-intensive practices that farmers might not be familiar with. The technical demands and how complicated certain methods appear to be is a barrier.
- **Lack of knowledge and information:** Farmers might lack awareness of available sustainable alternatives and proper knowledge about their methods of implementation. This includes uncertainty about their long-term effects on biodiversity and the environment as well as weed control efficacy. Education and information about effective alternative methods are crucial for their successful adoption but it was highlighted that there is a lack of skilled advisors available.
- **Risk and uncertainty:** Trying new methods involves a degree of risk, as farmers might be uncertain about the effectiveness and consistency of alternative weed control methods. Fear of crop loss or reduced yields can discourage experimentation. This barrier is linked with inconsistent results: the efficacy of alternative methods can vary based on factors such as weather conditions and weed species. If farmers experience inconsistent results, they might revert to herbicides for more predictable outcomes.
- **Time Constraints:** Sustainable alternatives like mechanical weeding or cover cropping might require more time and effort compared to conventional herbicide application. Many alternative methods require repeat application and more time-

consuming treatment for equivalent efficacy to herbicides. Farmers with limited time resources could find these methods challenging to adopt.

- **Peer Pressure:** Farmers might face social or peer pressure to conform to conventional practices. Concerns about being viewed as different or the uncertainty of how alternative methods will be perceived can influence decisions. Farmers indicated that they are less likely to use an alternative approach if they do not already know someone using it or have access to support from an experienced user. Negative feedback concerning alternative weed control methods did not emerge as a primary hindrance across the countries. Instead, the influence of peer-to-peer recommendations and personal experiences from individuals who have experimented with or consistently employed alternative approaches was notable.
- **Additional barriers:** Are there additional barriers (same questions for needs) that came out from focus groups and are common between several countries, but were not included in the suggested barriers (or needs) in the survey? For example, I am thinking about the lack of R&D for several alternative methods which are not yet very adapted for an efficient use (limited electrode efficacy for electrical weeding, lack of R&D on cover crop seeds, energy-consumption of electrical-weeding, the low work of speed of several tools...) which appeared to be quite important during the French focus group discussion.

Addressing these barriers requires a combination of educational extension programs, financial incentives, policy support, and research to demonstrate the viability and benefits of sustainable alternatives over the long term. The similarities between the general needs and barriers for alternative weed control across regions involved in OPER8 indicate that a harmonised strategy including education and outreach, demonstrations and peer to peer learning whilst providing technical support and training could be successful when implemented at an EU-wide level. However, it should also be noted that different regions have unique challenges and resources. Solutions should be adapted to the local context, considering factors like climate, soil type, and cropping system/ crop rotation.

Established and successful methods of alternative weed control are difficult to adapt between cropping sectors. This concern was raised by focus group members in Sweden and the UK. Whilst the needs and barriers for uptake of alternative weed control were similar between countries, the technical solutions available and feasible for each region may differ. Variable climatic conditions and cropping sectors representative between countries in different regions may restrict the extent to which alternative methods can be adapted for application across regions. In addition, some sustainable alternatives, like precision technology or organic farming practices, might require infrastructure changes that are not readily available in all regions.

Part. 3 Country specific notes and summaries

In the sections below, the country specific needs and barriers are reported and context provided from focus group discussions.

3.1 UK results

Overview of UK farmer and associated stakeholder profiles

In the UK, a total of 111 participants completed the survey, 110 stated that their country of residence was within the UK and one participant was from South Africa. Participants outside of the UK were removed for the analysis. Forty percent of the participants were farmers, the remaining 60% were non-farmers and constituted of; 23% agricultural advisors, 1% working for a governmental institution, 3% industry representatives, 28% researchers (academic or other) and 5% selected 'other'. Of the non-farmers, 87% had direct contact with farmers as part of their professional responsibilities. All participants had been working in the field of agriculture across a range of under 5 years to more than 20 years and 57% of all survey participants had been working in this field for more than 20 years.

Most participants agreed with five statements relating to the usage of chemical herbicides and the potential negative impacts that their use can have on the user, the environment and any resistance management efforts in place. Eleven percent or less of all participating farmers disagreed or strongly disagreed with these statements as shown in Figure 1.

FIGURE 1. PERCENTAGE RESPONSES OF FARMERS THAT PARTICIPATED IN THE ONLINE SURVEY RELATING TO FIVE STATEMENTS ON HERBICIDE USAGE AND THEIR IMPACTS ON THE USER, THE ENVIRONMENT AND THE DEVELOPMENT OF RESISTANT WEEDS.

Of the 44 participants that were farmers and completed the UK online survey, 77% indicated that cereals and oilseeds were the predominant crop type on their farm. Vegetable growers, vineyards, potatoes and sugar beet and other fruit or crops were also represented within the survey as shown in Figure 2.

FIGURE 2. PERCENTAGE OF FARMERS COMPLETING THE UK SURVEY AND THEIR SELECTION OF PREDOMINANT CROP TYPE (N=44).

When determining management styles of farmers, the management approaches were not defined within the survey, this led the participants to define and select the term they most identified with. The majority of farmers (43%) identified that they followed an IPM or IWM approach. This was closely followed by conventional farming (39%) and a smaller percentage of participants stated that they followed regenerative agricultural practices (9%), agroecological (2%) or conservation agriculture (2%) and the remaining 2% were organic. The size of farm managed by farmers completing the survey ranged from <5 to >1,000 ha and the median size of farm was within the size category 100.5-300 ha.

Herbicides were the most used weed control method identified, with 90% of farmers reliant on their application from the survey data. Other popular weed management approaches included cultivations (68%), hand weeding (61%), mechanical weeding (39%) and mowing (32%). The main disadvantages to these approaches were;

- Expense
- Time consumption
- Complicated methodology
- High carbon footprint

- Harmful to the environment
- Negative public opinions
- Low efficacy

Farmers were also asked which alternative methods they would be most interested in using but have not used yet. Results from these questions are shown in Figure 3.

FIGURE 3. PERCENTAGE OF FARMERS INTERESTED IN USING ALTERNATIVE METHODS OF WEED CONTROL FROM THE UK STAKEHOLDER ONLINE SURVEY.

Few participants had used camera guided hoes (2/44) despite this being identified as the most common method that farmers were interested in (64%). A larger proportion (17/44) of participants had used mechanical weeders, and this method was also identified by many farmers as something they had wanted to use but have not done so yet (50%). More than 40% of participants were interested in using robotics but no participants had ever used these approaches previously for weed control on their farm. There was interest in all alternative weed control approaches listed in Question 11 (Appendix 1) but, no farmers had previously used robotics, precision hoes, lasers, hot water/ foam, or microwave weed control methods in the UK. The specific reasons given for this were the expense of the equipment required, how complicated and time-consuming these methods may be and concerns whether these methods have low efficacy. In general, the main barriers to increase uptake of all methods of alternative weed control are shown in Figure 4.

FIGURE 4. PERCENTAGE AGREEMENT WITH SUGGESTED BARRIERS FOR UPTAKE OF ALTERNATIVE WEED CONTROL IN THE UK COMPLETED BY FARMER STAKEHOLDERS IN THE ONLINE SURVEY (N=44).

When asked what the most useful potential solutions would be to improve the uptake of alternative weed control in the UK, farmers ranked grants for the purchase of equipment, trials of alternative approaches and subsidies for environmentally friendly farming as the most useful, as shown in Figure 5. However, it should be noted that all the suggested approaches were mostly ranked as at least somewhat useful. It is likely that a combination of approaches would be essential to create a significant shift in the status quo for weed management.

FIGURE 5. PERCENTAGE RESPONSE OF FARMER PARTICIPANTS IN THE UK ONLINE SURVEY AND RANKING OF ACTIONS TO IMPROVE UPTAKE OF ALTERNATIVE WEED CONTROL BASED ON HOW USEFUL THESE ACTIONS WERE DEEMED TO BE (N=44).

The main barriers and useful potential solutions were ranked in a similar order by farmers and non-farmers in the UK online survey, indicating that advisors, researchers, and industry representatives are aware of the concerns and needs of farmers in the UK.

When asked where participants got the latest news in agriculture, staying up to date on legislative changes, state support, events, grants etc., survey participants in the UK indicated that they used several sources of information, but the most popular sources of information were at events and seminars, through newspapers and magazines, via the internet and directly from consultants and advisors. These avenues should be explored by WP5 of OPER8 to maximise communication and dissemination to stakeholders in the UK.

UK farmer needs, and associated barriers to, increasing uptake of alternative weed control solutions

The UK focus group was held online to give more people the opportunity to attend at a busy time in the UK farming calendar. In preparation for the workshop an agenda and recorded presentation of the UK online survey results was sent to all participants. In the focus group, the results of the survey were discussed with the NN to gain a deeper insight and contextual understanding behind the results. Thirteen people attended the focus group workshop, consisting of; six ADAS applied researchers, one arable farmer, two government policy workers, one horticulture agronomist, two Agriculture and Horticulture development board (AHDB) scientists and one technical officer (Linking Environment and Farming (LEAF)). The number of farmers in attendance was low due to the timing of the workshop (13/07/23), which is a busy time for UK arable farmers and horticulturalists.

The workshop began with a short introduction of all the participants and then an overview of the Oper8 project. Throughout the workshop, participants contributed mainly through discussion with note taking from ADAS. Following the introduction, the workshop was split into two main parts; the barriers to uptake of alternative weed control and the solutions to increase uptake. The needs and barriers of stakeholders to increase uptake of alternative weed control were discussed with the use of an online whiteboard⁴ to enable participation to be both verbal and written to maximise participation. The needs for increased alternative weed control uptake in the UK were split into five main categories and participants were asked to comment on each of these topics, and invited to identify any further barriers they were aware of. Five needs and associated barriers were agreed, listed with comments from the NN summarised below, in no particular order.

1. **The need:** Farmers need greater confidence in the efficacy of alternative weed control methods.

This is relevant across cropping systems and farm management styles across the UK.

Barrier: There is a lack of transparent, independent efficacy trials and demonstrations of alternative weed control methods.

Weed management efficacy, carbon release, and biodiversity impacts need to be rigorously assessed on a range of soil types. For example, there is a lack of quantitative data showing the effect of alternative approaches relative to conventional strategies in relation to weed control and profit margins. Some alternative weed methods include moving soil, such as mechanical inter and intra row hoes, which is contradictory to best practice for reducing carbon release from soils. It is likely that this barrier is exacerbated in arable production as smaller profit margins make it difficult to fund independent trials producing quality efficacy data.

Barrier: There is a lack of funding available for high quality independent trials.

The small marketing opportunities reduces the availability of funding for independent trials.

Barrier: Results from alternative weed control trials are not easily accessible to farmers.

The relatively lower uptake of alternative approaches in arable production reduces the likelihood that a farmer will know another farmer using an alternative approach and provide positive feedback. This was highlighted as an influential factor in increasing uptake of alternative weed control by the stakeholder survey. Similarly, a Defra funded study looking at farmer perspectives of weed management in UK organic systems supported these findings and showed that farmers who attended stakeholder workshops to share practical knowledge were more likely to uptake new novel weed control approaches⁵. The study found that learning weed control approaches from farmers within a network was the most useful form of knowledge dissemination (69%) while advisors and researchers were the least used source of weed management information (31% and

⁴ <https://whiteboard.office.com/>

⁵ Turner, R. J., Davies, G., Moore, H., Grundy, A. C. & Mead, A. (2007) Organic weed management: a review of the current UK farmer perspective. *Crop Protection*. 26 (3), 377-382.

38% respectively). Networking opportunities are therefore essential in which farmers can discuss research findings within established and trusted communities.

2. **The need:** Farmers need access to alternative weed control equipment.

Barrier: There is a lack of alternative weed control technology on the market, especially in UK arable production.

For example, handheld electrical weeders have been available since 2019, but the scale of production in arable farming makes this approach unfeasible for arable crops and tractor mounted electrical weeders are currently not available on the UK market.

Barrier: There is a large upfront investment from farmers for specialist equipment and some alternative approaches also have high running costs.

In UK horticulture, due to the higher revenue per hectare in comparison to arable production, alternative weed control uptake is generally greater than that for UK arable production. The high purchase price and running costs make some weed control approaches difficult to apply on a larger scale in arable production.

Barrier: The low uptake of technology by individual farmers in the UK reduces opportunities for machinery sharing as part of a cooperative.

The variable UK climate also provides short windows for use of agricultural machinery which can be difficult (but not impossible) to manage between multiple farms within a cooperative.

3. **The need:** Farmers need affordable alternative solutions for weed control.

Barrier: Specialist weed control equipment is expensive so it is difficult to justify its purchase and usage outside of high market value crops.

High investment and running costs are applicable to both the horticulture and arable sector, however the barrier is larger in arable systems where revenue per hectare is lower than in horticulture crops. This is reflected in the larger uptake of alternative solutions in horticultural crops.

Alternative/IPM solutions advocate multiple approaches which often require new investment in specialist equipment for systems where profit margins are already narrow. For example, the investment in a spot and spray system to reduce herbicide usage is estimated to cost approximately £100,000⁶. This would only be accessible to larger growers/contractors whose current machinery is coming to the end of its lifecycle. Investment in camera guided mechanical weeding is estimated to cost in the region of £25,000-£45,000⁷ so confidence in efficacy would be needed for an investment of this size. Alternative solutions, such as mechanical weeding, are generally more time intensive due to small machinery width and low travel speeds, increasing business running costs and reducing profit margins.

Barrier: Current grants for the purchase of specialist alternative weed control equipment are competitive and restricted by location.

Stakeholders considered grants for the purchase of equipment to be useful for the uptake of alternative weed control. But current equipment grants are funded under competitive applications⁸ or are catchment specific⁹. Widening the scope of uptake would enable more farmers to source grant funding for investment.

⁶ <https://www.fwi.co.uk/machinery/technology/french-firms-reveal-their-next-generation-spraying-tech>

⁷ <https://www.fwi.co.uk/machinery/root-crop-equipment/buyers-guide-camera-guided-sugar-beet-hoes>

⁸ <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/farming-equipment-and-technology-fund-fetf-2023/about-the-farming-equipment-and-technology-fund-fetf-2023>

⁹ <https://www.gov.uk/guidance/catchment-sensitive-farming-reduce-agricultural-water-pollution#countryside-stewardship>

Barrier: Sources of funding for environmentally friendly farming incentives are limited.

Financial incentives would be the fastest way to increase uptake of alternative weed control methods but sources of funding are limited. A small levy on herbicide sales (2%), such as the pesticide tax in Denmark, Sweden, Italy and France¹⁰, could generate a significant fund for investment in alternatives but this solution is often not seen favourably by UK government. In addition, stakeholders felt the incentivisation of uptake in the form of grants or taxes would need to be partnered with other factors such as herbicide loss to see widespread adoption of alternative solutions. The inclusion of 'reduced herbicide usage' payments into future SFI schemes, or similar ongoing subsidies, could be used alongside machinery grants to offset higher running costs.

4. The need: Farmers need alternative solutions that are more effective than herbicides and less time consuming to implement.

Barrier: Alternative weed control solutions are currently perceived as less effective than herbicides. The working width of most specialist equipment is generally smaller than current spray booms and requires slower travel speeds therefore increasing time for a single weeding operation. The lower efficacy per pass for some solutions results in more passes per crop to achieve similar levels of control to herbicides, for example trials of electrical weeding to control docks required three treatment timings to be equivalent to a herbicide application alone¹¹.

Barrier: Effective and established weed control solutions are difficult to transfer between different cropping systems.

For example, the use of camera guided mechanical which requires a high level of row definition across the crop to target inter and intra row weeds. Whilst these approaches have been successful in some horticultural systems, the narrower rows in arable crops may result in reduced accuracy if high weed density occurs. Smaller machinery is more suited to smaller scale of horticultural crops. But many of these crops are quick growing with limited timeframes to complete weed control, therefore the an increased number of weed passes brings further complications. Scaling up to arable systems would require wider machinery and/or increased time and labour input. The project stakeholders felt it was not currently feasible to provide effective control on larger scale arable crops due to the limited time, small working widths, and lower efficacy of the alternative solutions.

5. The need: Farmers need more information on alternative weed control solutions.

Barrier: There is a general lack of independent information on alternative weed control solutions, including the approaches available for different cropping systems as well as cost benefit analyses for each approach.

In the UK, farmers utilised a range of information sources to stay up to date on developments in agriculture. However, knowledge exchange efforts from research and innovation are minimal, limiting dissemination of innovative research to stakeholders.

Barrier: A main source of information to UK farmers on alternative weed control solutions, trials and weed control demonstrations is from organisations with a vested interest in the sale of a solution.

UK Summary

In the UK, a reliance on chemical herbicides was identified by farmers participating in the survey. However, there was strong agreement that long-term use of chemical herbicides can have detrimental effects on the user, the environment and can lead to the development of resistance in weed populations. Farmers are interested in alternative methods of weed control but there are key barriers preventing their uptake relating to a lack of access to equipment and information, the high cost associated with alternative equipment and no opportunities to access alternatives or speak with others that have experience with an alternative approach. To increase uptake of alternative weed control in the UK, stakeholders need a broad combination of tools to be implemented. There is a need for independent trials and demonstrations to increase knowledge and confidence in weed control solutions and for results to be disseminated effectively. The development of a database of solutions (Task 2.3) alongside the communication and

¹⁰ <https://www.pan-europe.info/issues/pesticide-taxation>

¹¹ <https://adas.co.uk/wp-content/uploads/2021/01/Electrical-Weed-Control-of-Docks-EIP-Report-FINAL.pdf>

dissemination from the Oper8 project (WP 5) will contribute to an increase in access to current knowledge. Farmers need greater access to equipment through trusted networks, or by exploring the potential for grants and subsidies to increase uptake. Solutions to address these needs, and the feasibility of solutions, will be explored further in the NAP (Task 2.4), with short and long-term steps outlined to increase the uptake of alternative weed control.

3.2 France results

Overview of French farmer and agriculture stakeholder profiles responding to the survey

The French survey results covered various stakeholders from the agriculture sector. The total number of respondents was 104, with 103 people from France, and 1 who did not answer for the location. Farmers made up 64% of the respondents, with 36% non-farmers, constating of 43% agricultural advisors, 24% other, 16% industry representatives, 8% governmental institution, 8% researchers. Age range categories of the respondents included 81% in the age range 31-60: 21% were 31-40, 34% were 41-50, 26% 51-60. The remaining respondents were 9% 21-30, and 11% were 61 and over. Regarding the education of the total respondents, 44% had a master's degree, 32% had a bachelor's degree, 20% had a vocational qualification, 3% had a PhD, and 1% ticked 'other'. Through vocational qualification, higher education, and continuous professional development courses, 87% of the respondents had a specialized education in the field of agriculture, and 13% not. Of the total respondents 61% had been working in the field of agriculture for 20 years and over, 30% between 5 and 20 years, 8% less than 5 years, and the remaining 2% could not answer.

Vineyards were the main crop for 96% of the farmers who responded the survey, and cereals/oilseeds farms only represented 4% of the farmer respondents. Among the farmer respondents, the size of farms and the management style for farming are presented below in Figure 6 and Figure 7. The size of farm managed ranged from <5 to 300 ha for 99% of the respondents, and the median size of farm was within the size category 30.1-100 ha. 76% of the farm sizes were between 10.1 ha and 100 ha, constituted of: 43% between 30.1 ha and 100 ha, and 33% between 10.1 ha and 30 ha. The farmer respondents' main management styles were 61% conventional and 18% organic. For the remaining answers, 9% described their management style as Integrated pest/weed management (IPM/IWM), and 7% as conservation / regenerative / agroecological agriculture and 4% 'other'.

FIGURE 6. SIZE OF FARMS AMONG THE FARMERS RESPONDENTS - FRANCE

FIGURE 7 - MANAGEMENT STYLE FOR FARMING PRACTICES AMONG THE FARMERS RESPONDENTS – FRANCE

Among the non-farmer respondents, 97% have direct contact with farmers, and only 3% have none. About 75% of the respondents considered farmers ask for their advice and consultation on weed control issues, and over 55% considered farmers follow their recommendations. These non-farmer respondents consider there is a shortage of information about alternative weed control methods even if they detect farmers are really interested in novel weed control methods, being mainly unsatisfied of their current weed control methods.

Among all the respondents, the main ways to get the latest news were via the internet, advisors, friends, acquaintances and colleagues, seminars, and events. Some other ways which are considered a bit less relevant but still commonly used: newspaper and magazine, and social media.

French survey results on current and alternative weed control solution use and opinion.

Opinion and knowledge on herbicide use.

The survey assessed the opinion of respondents regarding the herbicide use consequences on health, environment, and weed resistance. The results for farmers and non-farmers are in Figure 8 and Figure 9. Results show that among farmers, over 40% consider that herbicides do not contribute to the degradation of biodiversity and cannot enter the human body through food. Nevertheless, farmers agree on the fact that herbicides have carcinogenic properties, can accumulate in the environment, and have negative effects on organisms, and can cause weed resistance development. Non-farmers respondents have different opinion on these same statements (Figure 9). Most of them consider herbicides contribute to the degradation of biodiversity (>80%), have carcinogenic

properties (>90%), can accumulate in the environment, and have negative effects on organisms, and can cause weed resistance development. Non-farmers respondents are over 50% considering that herbicides can enter the human body through food.

FIGURE 8 - FIVE STATEMENTS WERE PROPOSED TO FRENCH FARMER RESPONDENTS ABOUT THEIR OPINION ON HERBICIDE USE RISKS.

FIGURE 9 - FIVE STATEMENTS WERE PROPOSED TO FRENCH NON-FARMER RESPONDENTS ABOUT THEIR OPINION ON HERBICIDE USE RISKS.

Current solutions and disadvantages.

The main current weed control methods are herbicides with 75% of the farmers using them on their farm, with mechanical weeding at 73%, and mowing at 57%. Other significant weed control methods were cultivations (30%), cultural control (25%), and hand weeding (22%). Some of the current methods are combinations of these listed solutions.

Specifically for herbicides, 33% of the farmer respondents considered that public have a negative opinion about the herbicide use, being a disadvantage, and 33% considered there is no significant drawback in this solution. Only 21% of the respondents considered herbicides harmful to the environment and human health. Contrary to that, 87% of the non-farmer respondents considered herbicides harmful for the environment and the human health.

For mechanical weeding, the main disadvantage is time-consuming. For mowing, the main disadvantages are first low efficacy, and second time-consuming.

The results for farmers' opinion about the general disadvantages of the currently used methods are presented in Figure 10. The main disadvantages are listed below:

- Expensive: 74% of the answers were agree or strongly agree. Selected in the answers for example for mulches, hand-weeding, robotics, cultivations and cultural control, mechanical weeding.
- Time-consuming: 72% of the answers were agree or strongly agree. Specifically for mechanical weeding, hand weeding, mowing, targeted herbicides.

- Public have a negative opinion towards the use of the method(s): 56% of the answers were agree or strongly agree.
- Complicated: 56% of the answers were agree or strongly agree.
- Customers demand the reduced use of the method(s): 51% of the answers were agree or strongly agree.

However, farmers do not consider these current methods have low efficacy (72% of the answers were disagree or strongly disagree to the Low efficacy option). Over 50% do not consider these current methods are harmful to the environment and human health.

FIGURE 10 – FRENCH FARMER RESPONDENTS' ANSWERS TO STATEMENTS ABOUT THE DISADVANTAGES OF THE CURRENT WEED CONTROL METHODS.

Main alternative weed control methods of interest, associated barriers, and levers for increasing the uptake.

Farmers are interested in various alternative weed control methods. Below is the list of the main weed control solutions of interest according to farmer survey respondents and the associated drawbacks to these solutions.

- camera guided hoes (43%): expensive.
- robotics (39%): expensive.
- mulches (36%): expensive, complicated, low efficacy.
- bioherbicides (34%): low efficacy, expensive.
- hot water/foam (30%): expensive.
- mechanical (27%): time-consuming, expensive.
- targeted herbicides (27%): expensive, time-consuming.
- other solutions (~20%): precision inter-intra row hoes, cultivations (cover crops...), mowing, hand-weeding, flame-weeding, microwave, laser.

The results for French farmers' opinion giving the reasons limiting the uptake of alternative weed control solutions are presented in Figure 11. The main reasons are listed below:

- time-consuming.
- too expensive.
- they have no access to the required equipment.

- no opportunities to test alternative weed control method(s) before investing.

Additionally, the non-farmers answers also commented on two other barriers: the high-carbon footprint of alternative solutions, and their complicated use.

FIGURE 11 - STATEMENTS REGARDING THE ALTERNATIVE WEED CONTROL METHODS, BASED ON FARMERS ANSWERS.

In Figure 12, it appears that various levers could be used for increasing the uptake of these alternative solutions. Over 50% of the French farmer respondents agreed or strongly agreed with the following:

- Grants for the purchase of equipment: linked to the 'too expensive' barrier both for current and alternative methods.
- Trials of alternative weed control methods: trials and communication on results of trials remain a good way to support farmers.
- Demonstration events of the methods of interest: related to WP5 with demo-events.
- Grants to establish trials to evaluate the effectiveness of the solutions: related to the need for more trials.

Additionally, non-farmers considered other relevant levers: subsidies for environmentally friendly farming, recommendations from other farmers and consultations with specialists or experienced users. Such demo-event activities and other workshops are being planned through the Oper8 project (WP5).

Opinion on which levers would help the uptake of alternative weed control / farmers

FIGURE 12 - STATEMENTS REGARDING THE WAYS TO INCREASE THE UPTAKE OF ALTERNATIVE WEED CONTROL, ACCORDING TO FARMER RESPONDENTS.

French focus group results

The focus group meeting focused on the existing alternative weed control methods with a group of 10 people in May 2023. The meeting focused on vineyards specifically. The group consisted of viticulture specialized people and general agriculture and agronomy specialists, representing the different stakeholders’ groups. It was held online with online post-it tools (Klaxoon tool) for both oral and written communication. Each participant had the opportunity to express their opinion, feedback, and knowledge, about the barriers and needs of these alternative solutions.

The outputs of the focus group discussions are presented below (Table 9). For each need or gap & barrier, the presence or absence of the issue has been evaluated for the listed alternative solutions.

TABLE 9 GAPS AND BARRIERS & NEEDS IDENTIFIED DURING THE FRENCH FOCUS GROUP MEETING, BASED ON THE ANALYSIS OF VARIOUS ALTERNATIVE SOLUTIONS.

GAPS & BARRIERS	mechanical weeding under the grapevine rows	cover crops under the grapevine rows	dead mulches under the grapevine rows	robots under the grapevine rows	thermal weeding under the grapevine rows	electrical weeding under the grapevine rows	vineyards grazing	combined solutions mechanical weeding + chemical weeding	MAIN BARRIERS & GAPS
Product R&D (tool not available yet for any situation or not adapted, raw material not available)	x	x	x	x		x			5
Complicated, high technicity level (fine-tuning, technical use, implementation...)	x	x	x	(x)			x		5
Low working speed	x	x		x	x	x			5
Expensive / purchase cost	x		x	x		x			4
Low efficiency	x				x	x	x		4
High energy consumption	x				x	x			3
Negative effect on grapevine (yield, vigor, growth stage...)		x	x				x		3
Not long-lasting		x	x		x				3
Wound risk on grapevine	x	x							2

NEEDS	mechanical weeding under the grapevine rows	cover crops under the grapevine rows	dead mulches under the grapevine rows	robots under the grapevine rows	thermal weeding under the grapevine rows	electrical weeding under the grapevine rows	vineyards grazing	combined solutions mechanical weeding + chemical weeding	MAIN NEEDS
R&D on tools (slope adapted, under row sowing engine, under row cover crop maintaining engine, under row spreading engine...)	x	x	x	x		x			5
Increasing the working speed	x	x		x	x	x			5
Lower purchase cost	x		x	x		x			4
Improved efficiency	x					x			2
R&D on raw material (cover crops seeds, mulches...) and ease-of-access		x	x						2
Reduced energy consumption					x	x			2
Increase of service providers and engine sharing between farmers	x			x					2
Changes in regulations (robots, glyphosate for combined solutions...)				x				x	2
Tractor drivers training	x								1
Help/Training on engine fine-tuning	x								1

Needs, gaps, and barriers for the uptake of alternative weed control in French viticulture

The survey gave general information about the opinion of farmers and non-farmers stakeholders about the current and alternative weed control methods. The focus group meeting gave more precise and additional information about the barriers farmers are facing and needs for increasing uptake. Below is a list of the barriers & gaps and needs with crossed information from the survey (farmers and non-farmers) and focus group discussion.

BARRIERS & GAPS:

- **Time-consuming:** Many methods require a lot of time to have good results, which results in lower overall efficiency. Cover crops management, mechanical weeding, robots, thermal and electrical weeding under the row of grapevine, have low working-speeds. Some of these methods also require additional treatments because they do not have a long-lasting effect, or additional hand-weeding for example for the trunk area. Also, considering the amount of time and money necessary to implement dead mulches like felt, they are not long-lasting enough.
- **Expensive:** This barrier refers to the high purchase costs of innovative tools, or the high amount of money to buy multiple tools, for example in mechanical weeding where a good result is reached through multiple tool complementarity. In these cases, these purchases are not affordable for small scale farms. Additionally, the high energy consumption of some methods makes the cost higher. Also, this barrier is related to time-consuming considering the multiple treatments or low working-speed and low efficiency.
- **No access to the required equipment, lack of options for every farm situation:** Regarding cover crop method in vineyards, there is no choice of selection on seeds with reduced height, limited competition for nutrients, and good soil coverage capacity. Regarding mechanical weeding, tools are not adapted for narrow row vineyards (<2 m width between the rows), or for slopes.
- **No opportunities to test** alternative weed control method(s) before investing.
- **Complicated use of alternative methods**, high technicity level: for mechanical weeding, active tools like hydraulic plough require a high technicity level to work without damaging the trunks. Additional fine-tuning is also necessary to improve the efficacy of the tool.
- **Impact on crops:** The use of some methods such as cover crops can generate yield and vigor loss, time lag in the growth stages; mechanical weeding presents a wound risk on the trunk and root system. Dead mulches can reduce infiltration for small amounts of water. Mechanical weeding induces a loss of organic matter.
- **High-carbon footprint** of some alternative solutions.

NEEDS:

- Grants for purchase and lower purchase costs: Tools, engines, seeds, and novel methods need to be affordable for a wide uptake among the farmers community. These grants would also cover the additional time spent on these alternative solutions, compared to herbicide use.
- Trials and research grants for trials: New and existing alternative solutions still need to be tested for various situations and local contexts. Numbers and precise results close to on-farm situation are necessary.

- Peer-to-peer learning through demo-event, recommendations from other farmers and consultations with specialists or experienced users: Knowledge and feedback exchanges are relevant for farmers as they provide on-farm situation examples with technical advice.
- Subsidies for environmentally friendly farming: Supporting specific kind of farming is a way to fund alternative solutions by selecting the less harmful methods with specifications.
- Research and development:
 - o On product and tool: to improve working speed, efficacy, energy-consumption, specific situation like slope adaptation; to develop under grapevine rows sowing and maintaining treatments. It can also be tool development for camera-guided hoes, given that farmers have a high interest in this method, or for electrical weeding which requires an improved mechanical design of the moving electrode, for example.
 - o On raw materials: cover crop seeds adapted to the main crop requirements. It can also be about bioherbicide development, considering this is among the alternative solutions of interest for farmers.
- Facilities, service providers and engine sharing: It is about sharing expenses, and access to quality work. For example, for small scale farms where the purchase of several complementary tools is not affordable, sharing engines between farmers can help to prevent this barrier. Service providers can also allow a good work quality due to qualification on the work expected. Also, an increase of availability of cover crop seeds is required through agriculture facilities.
- Training of tractor drivers and training for fine-tuning of the tools and engines: The high technicity of active tools require a good knowledge of the tools for work optimization and limited impact on the grapevine.
- Changes in regulation: This was about regulations on autonomous robot use that currently do not allow the robot to be left alone in the field. It was also about the combination of non-chemical solutions with herbicide use, which would require to increase the current threshold on glyphosate use.

French summary

Multiple alternative weed control solutions are of interest for farmers and reflect the wide variety of farm sizes, management style, and geographical constraints. The various categories are 1) innovative ag-tech solutions such as camera guided hoes, robotics, other novel solutions like hot foam/water; 2) cultivations and cultural control with mulches, cover crops, mowing; 3) bioherbicides and targeted herbicides; 4) mechanical weeding which is currently common but still present important disadvantages. Other solutions like vineyards grazing by pigs or sheep have been discussed and currently exist, with advantages such as the high-quality fodder for spontaneous cover crops which can be of interest for a shepherd. Rising awareness about the consequences of herbicide use and the need to switch to alternative methods is still needed, considering that only 21% of farmers consider herbicide to be harmful for health and the environment. Awareness and uptake of alternative weed control can be stimulated through different levers: grants covering purchase costs and business running costs; additional trials for technical content; demo-event, peer-to-peer learning and discussions with experienced users and experts; research and development on all type of solutions to improve efficiency, availability, adaptation; subsidies for environmentally friendly farming; and availability of service providers, training, fine-tuning support, are among the needs identified through this project task.

3.3 Italy results

Overview of Italy farmer and agriculture stakeholder profiles

For Italy, 77 people responded to the survey, 48% of which were farmers, and 52% were non-farmers. These latter were represented mostly by researchers (42.5%), followed by agricultural advisors (22.5%), members of governmental institutions (12.5%),

policymakers (10%), others (10%), industry representatives (2.5%). For age, 67.5% of the respondents were over 40 years old. Most of the total respondents own a university degree (with 37 having a master's degree and 5 having a BSc degree). Given the high presence of researchers among the respondents, 18 participants also hold a Ph.D. title. Only 12 people had no specialized education in the field of agriculture. 75% of the total respondents have been working in the field of agriculture for 20 years and over.

Among farmers, the most represented class of farm was between 30 and 100 ha (27%) (Figure 13). Only 3% responded from very big farms with an acreage of more than 1000 ha. Whereas, 16% of farmers had up to 5 ha of farm land. In accordance with the acreage, for the 75% of the respondents the main crops are cereals and oilseed crops (Figure 14). The second most popular crops were vineyards (11%) and other crops (11%). Very few field vegetable growers (3%) completed the cluster of farmers, whereas no farmers specialised on potatoes or sugar beet were present. The group of the farmers was equally subdivided in conventional, IPM-based and organic. Two farmers declared to apply conventional agriculture techniques and one defined his/her management as “agroecological”.

FIGURE 13 - SIZE OF FARMS AMONG THE FARMERS RESPONDENTS – ITALY (N=37)

FIGURE 14 – MAIN CROPS AMONG THE FARMERS RESPONDENTS – ITALY (N=37).

Although most of the non-farmer respondents were researchers, 85% of them declared to work closely with the farmers. This highlights the emergent trends in agricultural research to carry out participatory or on-farm research activities, in which farmers are directly or indirectly involved. Advisory on weed management was reported for 50% of the respondents, who declared that farmers are not fully satisfied of their current weed management and 77.5% of them declared there is an evident lack of information on alternative methods to herbicide use.

Italian survey results on current and alternative weed control solution use and opinion

Opinion and knowledge on herbicide use.

The survey assessed the opinion of respondents regarding the herbicide use consequences on health, environment, and weed resistance. The results for farmers and non-farmers are in Figure 15 and Figure 16. The bar charts show that there were different beliefs between farmers and non-farmers. Farmers showed to be less prone to believe to the hazardousness of herbicides in terms of carcinogenic properties, contribution to biodiversity loss and accumulation in human body through food intake. Non farmers showed instead a clear trust in these assumptions, which gained around 80% of consensus. For the last two assumptions (negative effects on organisms and herbicide resistance development), the two groups of respondents showed more similar opinions. In particular, farmers have a clear perception of the risks of development of herbicide resistance in weeds, one environmental but also technical problem they have to deal with in their everyday activities. Herbicide resistance is also a huge economic problem and that is why this trend in the answer is not surprising at all.

Italian results show that among farmers over 40% consider that herbicides do not contribute to the degradation of biodiversity and cannot enter the human body through food. Nevertheless, farmers agree on the fact that herbicides have carcinogenic properties, can accumulate in the environment and have negative effects on organisms, and can cause weed resistance development. Non-farmers respondents have different opinion on these same statements. Most of them consider herbicides contribute to the degradation of biodiversity, have carcinogenic properties, can accumulate in the environment and have negative effects on organisms, and can cause weed resistance development. Non-farmers respondents are over 50% considering that herbicides can enter the human body through food.

FIGURE 15 - FIVE STATEMENTS WERE PROPOSED TO ITALIAN FARMER RESPONDENTS ABOUT THEIR OPINION ON HERBICIDE USE RISKS (N=37).

FIGURE 16 - FIVE STATEMENTS WERE PROPOSED TO ITALIAN NON-FARMER RESPONDENTS ABOUT THEIR OPINION ON HERBICIDE USE RISKS (N=40).

Current solutions and disadvantages.

The most common current weed control methods applied by Italian farmers are shown in Figure 17.

FIGURE 17. MOST POPULAR WEED CONTROL TACTICS APPLIED BY THE ITALIAN FARMERS PARTICIPATING TO THE SURVEY (N=37)

The main current weed control methods are herbicides, mechanical weed control and cultural control. Also mowing and cultivations were quite extensively reported. Clearly, the answers of the farmers reveal there is a combination of different methods, with conventional farmers applying not only herbicides but also other tactics shared with organic farmers. Interestingly, some innovative tactics, such as laser weeding, cultivar choice, camera driven hoeing and allelopathy) were reported as current weed control methods.

Generally speaking, farmers expressed a clear consensus on economic (“expensive”) and operative (“time consuming”) limitations of the IWM tactics currently applied in their farms, irrespective of what the tactics are, if herbicide-based or not (Figure 18).

The results for farmers’ opinion about the disadvantages of each of the most common currently used methods are listed below:

- Herbicides: 45% of the respondents stated the major limitation is the negative public opinion, whereas only 14% identified environmental hazard as the major cons for this method.
- Mechanical weeding: 15% of the respondent stated mechanical methods are time consuming. The same percentage was also obtained for “complicated” and “expensive”. Interestingly, two farmers identified in environment-related issues (GHG emissions, environmental hazardousness) the major limitation for these methods. The 27% of the respondent declared no disadvantages.
- Cultivations: 31% of the farmers declared no disadvantages, whereas 15% reported time consumption as the major drawback and another 15% pointed out the GHG emission issue.
- Cultural methods: 37% of the respondents declared no disadvantages, whereas 15% and 19% identified, respectively, in time consumption and difficulties in the implementation (“complicated”) the major limitations. Nobody reported on environmental issues.
- Mowing: an equal number of respondents (21%) identified the major limitations in time consumption and low efficacy. Others reported problems in the costs (“expensive”) or difficulties (“complicated”).

Opinion on current methods on farms / farmers

FIGURE 18. ITALIAN FARMER RESPONDENTS' ANSWERS TO STATEMENTS ABOUT THE DISADVANTAGES OF THE CURRENT WEED CONTROL METHODS.

Main alternative weed control methods of interest, associated barriers, and levers for increasing the uptake

Farmers are interested in various alternative weed control methods (Figure 19). Clearly, the major preference of Italian farmers came to direct methods based on precision agriculture technologies (e.g., camera-driven hoeing or see and spray herbicide application), but also flaming, robotics, laser and bioherbicides are attracting farmers' attention. Cultural control methods are another hot spot, presumably for conventional farmers in particular.

Alternative methods farmers are interested to try

FIGURE 19. ITALIAN FARMER RESPONDENTS' PREFERENCES FOR ALTERNATIVE WEED CONTROL METHODS (N=37).

For each of these alternative weed control methods, the surveyed farmers identified the major disadvantages (Figure 20).

FIGURE 20. ITALIAN FARMER RESPONDENTS' PREFERENCES FOR ALTERNATIVE WEED CONTROL METHODS (N=37).

Expensiveness was identified as the major disadvantage for robotics (100%), flame weeding (50%), mulches (67%) and hand weeding (67%).

Low efficacy was selected for bioherbicides (100%), microwaves (100%), electrical/hot foam weeding (100%), flame weeding (50%), varietal choice (50%), mowing (33%), cultural control (25%) and mechanical weeding (29%).

Time consumption was attributed to precision inter- or intra-row hoeing (50%), hand weeding (25%), cultural control (20%) and cultivations (33%).

Mowing and cultural control were also labelled as “complicated”, whereas for herbicides consumers’ preference for alternative methods is clearly perceived as the major limitation by farmers.

Mulching and mechanical weed control were judged also harmful for the environment.

No significant disadvantages were identified for alleopathy and camera-guided hoeing, but in these cases there were only 1 respondent.

In general, for all the listed alternative weed control methods, farmers identified the barriers for their wide adoption, as showed by Figure 21.

Current barriers for alternative weed control uptake / farmers

FIGURE 21. STATEMENTS REGARDING THE ALTERNATIVE WEED CONTROL METHODS, BASED ON FARMERS ANSWERS.

As showed in Figure 21, farmers agreed or strongly agreed especially on the following barriers:

- Methods are time consuming.
- Solutions are too expensive.
- No opportunity to test innovative solutions before investing on them.
- No access to required equipment.
- No skilled advisory available.
- Lack of information.

Non farmers respondents neglected the economic aspects, whereas they expressed an even higher consensus on unavailability of specific advisory, impossibility to test the method before adoption and lack of information (Figure 22).

FIGURE 22. STATEMENTS REGARDING THE ALTERNATIVE WEED CONTROL METHODS, BASED ON NON-FARMERS ANSWERS

The levers that could be foreseen to increase the uptake of these alternative solutions are reported for farmers and non-farmers in Figure 23 and Figure 24, respectively.

Over 50% of the farmer respondents agreed or strongly agreed with the following:

- Need: Grants for the purchase of equipment: selected by more than 80% of the farmers, linked to the ‘too expensive’ barrier both for current and alternative methods.
- Need: Consultations with a specialist or experienced user: more than 70% of the farmers expressed this preference, as they need support for adopting novel strategies, especially in the transition phase or more regularly for long-term perspective methods, such as cultural control.
- Need: Trials of alternative weed control methods: linked to lack of information and proofs of efficacy, possibly connected to the idea of on-farm trials and learn by doing approach.
- Need: Demonstration events of the methods of interest: related to the need of peer-to-peer knowledge transfer and of showcasing;
- Need: Grants to establish trials to evaluate the effectiveness of the solutions: related to the need of local fine-tuning of alternative method in the specific farmers’ conditions.

Additionally, non-farmers considered other relevant levers: subsidies for environmentally friendly farming, recommendations from other farmers and regulation levers connected to public opinion and consumers’ preferences (Figure 24).

Opinion on which levers would help the uptake of alternative weed control /farmers

FIGURE 23. STATEMENTS REGARDING THE WAYS TO INCREASE THE UPTAKE OF ALTERNATIVE WEED CONTROL, ACCORDING TO ITALIAN FARMER RESPONDENTS.

FIGURE 24. STATEMENTS REGARDING THE WAYS TO INCREASE THE UPTAKE OF ALTERNATIVE WEED CONTROL, ACCORDING TO ITALIAN NON-FARMER RESPONDENTS.

Italian focus group results

In Italy, the focus group set-up and activity have been delayed due to operational difficulties in assembling people able to represent such a wide and diversified AKIS, given the high variability in pedo-climatic and socio-economic conditions at national level.

The composition of the focus group has been defined as follow:

- 3 farmers: covering arable crops/field vegetables and vineyards, IPM-based and organic farming sectors.
- 3 advisors: covering arable crops, field vegetables and vineyards.
- 1 officer from Regional Phytosanitary Services.
- 1 officer from the Ministry of Agriculture.
- 2 representatives from the industry (1 for farm machinery sector, 1 for seed companies).
- 2 national experts from academia.

The first focus group meeting will be held online in early September 2023. Therefore, the outcomes of the focus group cannot be part of this deliverable and will be supplemented at a later stage and at earliest possibility.

Italy survey summary

Similarly, to other countries, also in Italy farmers resulted to be interested in testing weed control solutions alternative to herbicides. This reflects the composition of the farmers involved in the survey, comprising both conventional and organic farmers, whose motivations were different but led to similar preferences. Conventional farmers are looking for alternatives to herbicides majorly because of well experienced problems of herbicide resistance and because their awareness about market drivers toward a greener agricultural production. Organic farming, by definition, relies upon the integration of multiple, non-herbicide based IWM tactics, often inconsistent to each other or difficult to design or implement. Mechanization and technology-based solutions (e.g., camera-guided hoes, flaming, precision application of herbicides) resulted to be attractive also because of the high presence of extensive farms. Agroecological solutions, such as mulching and cover crops, were particularly attractive for organic farmers. The adoption of alternative methods is unanimously considered hampered by economic, operational and knowledge limitations. Possible levers identified include production of new knowledge for those solutions for which poor information is available, case-sensitive and locally fine-tuned trials, subsidies for facilitating access to new technologies.

3.4 Greece results

Overview of Greek farmer and associated stakeholder profiles

It is essential to ensure that the survey is distributed and conducted across different organisations of Greece. Different stakeholders might have specific agricultural challenges and practices that should be accounted for in the survey. Before finalizing the survey, one focus group was established including ten people, to ensure that the questions align with the overall objectives of the research or study. This helped in gathering meaningful data and achieving the desired outcomes.

Out of the total 92 responses, 64 were from farmers, and the remaining 28 responses came from non-farmers (Figure 25). An online interview with the focus group was conducted on 14 July 2023 including 10 members from academia industry and policy, presenting the main findings of the survey in pptx format as follows:

Participant Information

- Farmers 70%
- Agricultural Advisors 8%
- Academics / Researchers 18%
- Government Organizations 1%
- Industry representatives 2%

FIGURE 25. PARTICIPANT INFORMATION

It appears that the survey includes a diverse range of participants from different backgrounds related to agriculture and farming. Here are some observations and potential considerations for the survey based on this participant distribution:

- **Farmer Representation:** With 70% of the participants being farmers, it is important to ensure that the survey questions are relevant to their experiences, challenges, and perspectives. Tailor the questions to address specific issues faced by farmers in Greece, regarding alternative weed control.
- **Inclusion of Agricultural Advisors and Academics:** The 8% of agricultural advisors and 18% of academics/researchers can bring valuable expertise and insights to the survey. Consider including questions that encourage these participants to share their knowledge, research findings, and recommendations to benefit the farming community.
- **Low Government Organization Participation:** With only 1% representation from government organizations, it might be challenging to draw comprehensive conclusions about government policies and their impact on agriculture. Through the focus group conducted, the participation from this group was increased to obtain a more well-rounded perspective.
- **Industry Representatives:** The 2% of industry representatives may have valuable insights into the agricultural supply chain, technology, and market trends. Their input could be valuable in understanding the link between farmers and industry.

The survey captured a broad range of age groups (Figure 25), which can provide valuable insights into how different generations perceive and engage with agriculture in Greece. It is obvious that the age groups 31-40 (32 participants) and 41-50 (32 participants) combined represent a substantial portion of the participants (69.6%). These age groups might be in the active phase of their careers and farming practices, making their responses particularly relevant for understanding current challenges and trends in the agricultural sector. The 15.2% (14 participants) of respondents in the 21-30 age group might offer insights into the perspectives and ideas of the younger generation in the agricultural sector. Their responses could indicate future trends and potential changes in the industry. While the 61+ age group constitutes 3.3% of the participants, their experiences and accumulated knowledge can be highly valuable. Consider tailoring some questions to capture their wisdom and insights from years of farming or involvement in the agriculture sector. Overall, the age distribution in the survey offers an opportunity to gain a comprehensive understanding of the agriculture sector's dynamics and how it is perceived by different generations in Greece.

The survey also reveals a good representation of participants across different experience levels, ranging from newcomers to seasoned professionals. The majority of participants fall into the categories of "Between 10 and 20 years" and "More than 20 years." Their extensive experience can provide valuable insights into long-term trends, challenges, and best practices in the agriculture sector. The participants with 5 to 10 years of experience form a significant portion of the respondents. These individuals might offer a perspective that bridges the gap between newcomers and seasoned professionals. While the number of participants with up to 5 years of experience is relatively low, their responses can shed light on the challenges faced by those entering the agricultural field. Given the presence of respondents with over 20 years of experience, consider including questions that seek their expert opinions on the evolution of agriculture in Greece and their insights into potential future developments.

Overview of Greek farm structure and land size distribution

The land size distribution in the survey provides an opportunity to gain insights into the diversity of farming operations in Greece.

FIGURE 26. CROP STRUCTURE DATA

The survey includes farmers with a diverse range of land sizes, from small-scale farmers with less than 5 hectares to larger operations with over 100 hectares (Figure 26). Participants with up to 5 hectares represent a significant portion of the respondents. Their responses can provide valuable insights into the challenges faced by small-scale farmers and their unique perspectives on agriculture. The participants in the 5.1 to 30-hectare range encompass a substantial number of respondents. Although participants with land sizes over 100 hectares are fewer in number, their responses can offer insights into the challenges and opportunities faced by larger agricultural operations in Greece.

Also, different farming methods are represented in the survey. There is a dominance of Conventional Agriculture, with 63% of participants practicing conventional agriculture, this way, it is essential to understand the prevailing practices and challenges associated with conventional farming in Greece. The participation of 22% of respondents in IPM indicates a significant interest in sustainable and environmentally friendly pest control methods. The 16% of respondents practicing organic farming signifies a notable presence of sustainable and chemical-free agriculture.

It is also obvious the dominance of Cereals/Oilseeds, with 22% of participants growing cereals and oilseeds, appearing to be a significant agricultural sector in Greece. The participation of 12% of respondents in vineyards suggests a notable presence of viticulture in the country. Investigate the practices and factors that contribute to the success of vineyards in Greece. 14% of participants grow other crops and the 11% involved in other fruits indicate agricultural diversity in the survey. There is a low representation of vegetables, with only 3% of respondents growing, while representing a smaller proportion (1%), potatoes and sugar beet.

View on the effects of herbicides on humans and the environment?

View on the effects of herbicides on humans and the environment

Website www.oper8.eu

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

FIGURE 27. OPINION ON THE EFFECTS OF HERBICIDES ON HUMANS AND THE ENVIRONMENT FROM GREEK SURVEY

The data (Figure 27), indicate that a significant number of respondents agree or strongly agree with the potential negative effects of herbicides on weed resistance, environmental accumulation, human exposure through food, biodiversity degradation, and certain herbicides' carcinogenic properties. However, there is also a notable portion of respondents who selected "Neither agree nor disagree" or "N/A / I don't know," especially for other people category, suggesting a range of opinions and awareness levels among the participants.

Overview of current methods of weed control.

The data reveal diverse opinions among the participants regarding the current weed control methods on farms. Some methods receive higher agreement in specific categories, such as cost-effectiveness or environmental impact, while others have more evenly distributed responses across the scale. These insights can help in identifying areas where improvements or adjustments may be needed to optimize weed management practices in the context of farmers' concerns and preferences.

Agreement with statements relating to current methods on farm

Website www.oper8.eu

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme under Grant Agreement NO 101060591

FIGURE 28. AGREEMENT WITH STATEMENTS RELATING TO CURRENT METHODS ON FARM FROM GREEK SURVEY

The survey results indicate that several factors play a significant role in influencing Greek farmers' decisions to stick with their current weed control methods rather than adopting alternative approaches (Figure 28). Among these factors, cost, environmental concerns, and time constraints emerge as prominent determinants. The financial implications associated with current methods prove to be a primary factor in farmers' decision-making process. Financial concerns are often intertwined with the uncertainty of the returns on investment, making farmers hesitant to bear the upfront costs without a clear understanding of the benefits over the long term. Also increasing awareness of the environmental impact of conventional weed control methods has led to a growing interest in more sustainable practices. Greek farmers are seeking also methods that not only deliver effective weed control but also integrate seamlessly into their existing routines, minimizing disruptions and time consumption and allowing for efficient resource allocation.

According to the discussions of the focus group, these three factors - cost, environmental concerns, and time constraints - stand out as the predominant factors shaping the preference for current weed control methods, it's essential to recognize that the adoption landscape is multi-faceted. Other factors, such as the lack of information, access to equipment, and concerns about method effectiveness, contribute to the overall decision-making framework. Strategies to promote alternative methods should thus be tailored to address these specific barriers, addressing financial viability, providing clear environmental benefits, and ensuring that these methods align with the practical constraints faced by farmers.

FIGURE 29. METHODS OF CONTROL CURRENTLY USED

Herbicides are the most widely employed weed control method in Greece, with participants reporting few significant drawbacks other than their high cost and harmful effects on the environment (Figure 29). Mechanical control, involving machinery for weeding, comes in second place, but participants mention its time-consuming nature, limited efficacy, and high carbon footprint. Mowing takes the third spot, but a considerable number of participants express concerns about its costliness. Hand weeding, though used by fewer participants, is acknowledged as effective but demanding in terms of labor and time investment. Cultivations are adopted by several participants, who highlight its high cost, limited effectiveness, and significant carbon footprint. Camera-guided hoes, though employed by a small percentage of respondents, show potential for precise weed control, and warrant further investigation. Cultural control methods, encompassing agronomic practices for weed management, are relatively less utilized, with only a small proportion of respondents employing them. Mulches and varietal choice, although used by a smaller proportion of participants, are environmentally friendly approaches deserving of deeper exploration. The data also includes novel weed control methods like flame weeding, hot water/foam, robotics, microwave, bioherbicides, laser, and allelopathy. While their usage is minimal, they present potential areas for future research and development.

Weed control methods that they have used but do not use anymore, their main disadvantage (and why they no longer use the method)

FIGURE 30. WEED CONTROL METHODS THAT THEY HAVE USED BUT DO NOT USE ANYMORE, THEIR MAIN DISADVANTAGE (AND WHY THEY NO LONGER USE THE METHOD)

Hand weeding is the predominant method that has been used in the past but is no longer favored (Figure 30). The main drawback is likely the high labor demand, making it physically demanding and time-consuming, especially in large fields. Following hand weeding, mowing is another method that has been discontinued. Its primary disadvantages are its time-consuming nature and low efficacy, as it may not effectively eliminate weeds with deep root systems, and regrowth can occur quickly after mowing. Mechanical methods are also among the discontinued techniques, and their main disadvantage lies in their labor-intensive and time-consuming nature, necessitating substantial effort and resources from farmers.

Weed control methods that they are aware of/interested in but never used (and why)

FIGURE 31. WEED CONTROL METHODS THAT THEY ARE AWARE OF/INTERESTED IN BUT NEVER USED (AND WHY)

The data indicate that the participants have different levels of awareness and interest in the alternative weed control methods (Figure 31). Some methods, like flame weeding, hot water/foam, and robotics, have garnered significant attention and interest from a larger number of respondents. In contrast, methods such as mowing, hand weeding, varietal choice, microwave, laser, and allelopathy appear to have lower awareness and interest among the participants. Interestingly, cost is consistently identified as the

primary perceived disadvantage for the majority of these methods. This suggests that the financial aspect plays a crucial role in shaping farmers' attitudes towards adopting alternative weed control approaches. Addressing the cost concerns and providing information on the benefits and effectiveness of these methods may help increase their adoption among farmers in Greece.

The insights from the focus group discussions suggest that promoting the adoption of alternative weed control methods could be achieved through several strategies. Increasing awareness and understanding among farmers can be accomplished by providing more information about these methods. Demonstrations can showcase their effectiveness and practical application, instilling confidence in farmers. Offering opportunities for farmers to test these methods on their own fields allows them to see the benefits firsthand, making them more likely to adopt them.

Greek farmer needs, and associated barriers to, increasing uptake of alternative weed control solutions

FIGURE 32. HOW FAR DO YOU AGREE WITH THE FOLLOWING STATEMENTS

On the farmers perspective, most respondents (41 agree and 14 strongly agree) felt that there is indeed a lack of information available about alternative weed control methods (Figure 32). A significant number of respondents (27 agree and 10 strongly agree) express concerns about the absence of skilled advisors or consultants. One notable finding is the relatively high perception of low efficiency in alternative weed control methods, with 28 respondents agreeing and 4 strongly agreeing. This indicates that efficacy is an important consideration when farmers contemplate adopting these alternatives. The lack of access to necessary equipment emerges as a significant concern for many farmers, as indicated by 41 respondents agreeing and 11 strongly agreeing. This highlights the need to address equipment availability to make alternative methods more accessible. Negative reviews about alternative weed control methods are of considerable concern to respondents, with 28 agreeing and 19 strongly agreeing. Overcoming such negative perceptions is crucial in encouraging farmers to embrace these alternatives. A substantial number of respondents express the need for more opportunities to test alternative weed control methods before making significant investments, with 33 agreeing and 12 strongly agreeing. Providing trial opportunities can help instill confidence in farmers and lead to more informed decisions. Cost concerns are also significant, with 32 respondents agreeing and 22 strongly agreeing that alternative weed control methods may be too expensive. Addressing affordability issues can be instrumental in encouraging farmers to adopt these methods. The perception that regulations hinder the use of certain methods is quite prevalent, with 28 respondents agreeing and 19 strongly agreeing. Advocating for more flexible guidelines can help overcome regulatory obstacles and promote the adoption of alternative methods. Many respondents' express concerns about time-consuming methods, with 30 agreeing and 16 strongly agreeing. Promoting more efficient and time-saving alternatives can be key in encouraging their adoption.

These responses were varying levels of agreement among the focus group participants regarding the challenges and obstacles related to the adoption of alternative weed control methods. Some issues, such as the lack of information and access to equipment, are strongly agreed upon, while others, like negative reviews and time-consuming methods, show a more mixed range of opinions.

Understanding these concerns can help address them effectively and facilitate the uptake of alternative weed control methods among farmers.

Agreement with statements relating to alt methods

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FIGURE 33. HOW FAR DO YOU AGREE WITH THE FOLLOWING STATEMENTS?

The data highlight various barriers to the uptake of alternative weed control methods (Figure 33), including limited information, absence of skilled advisors, concerns about efficiency and effectiveness, limited access to equipment, negative reviews, lack of testing opportunities, high costs, regulatory constraints, time constraints, and environmental considerations. Addressing these concerns and providing targeted support and information could play a vital role in encouraging farmers to adopt alternative weed control methods and promoting more sustainable practices in agriculture.

The focus group participants emphasized that farmers might encounter difficulties due to insufficient information about alternative methods, which could hinder their adoption. The lack of skilled advisors or consultants was also noted as a potential obstacle in adopting alternative weed control methods. Moreover, limited access to necessary equipment was reported as a barrier, along with concerns about the effectiveness of these alternative methods. Additionally, negative feedback or reviews from others were mentioned as factors that could influence farmers' decisions. Cost concerns related to alternative weed control methods were also brought to light. The need for more opportunities to test these methods before committing to them was highlighted during the discussions, as well as the possibility that time constraints might discourage farmers from adopting certain alternative methods. Lastly, the lack of familiarity with other farmers using alternative methods was mentioned as another factor that might influence farmers' adoption decisions.

How do you perceive your contact with farmers?

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FIGURE 34. HOW DO YOU PERCEIVE YOUR CONTACT WITH FARMERS?

For the question "Farmers ask for your advice or consultation on weed control issues," a significant number of respondents (Strongly agree) confirm that many farmers actively seek advice or consultation on weed control matters (Figure 34). This indicates a high level of engagement and trust in the surveyor's expertise from the farming community.

Regarding the question "Farmers follow your recommendations," the majority of respondents (Agree) indicate that farmers generally follow the recommendations provided by the surveyor. This suggests that the advice given is perceived as valuable and practical, leading to its implementation by farmers.

For the question "Farmers are satisfied with their current weed control methods," several respondents (Neutral) suggest that farmers might have mixed feelings about their current weed control methods. While some express satisfaction, others might be experiencing dissatisfaction with their existing practices. As for the question "Farmers are interested in novel weed control methods," participants indicate that farmers, in general, are open to exploring new weed control methods. Some respondents even express a strong interest in adopting innovative approaches to manage weeds effectively. Regarding the question "There is a shortage of information about alternative weed control methods for farmers," 16 respondents (Neutral) and 5 respondents (Agree) imply that there might be a lack of information or awareness about alternative weed control methods among farmers. This finding highlights an opportunity to improve the availability of resources and education to better support farmers in their weed management practices.

The focus group declared the contact with farmers has a positive impact, with many farmers seeking advice and following recommendations. However, potential information gaps have to be addressed along with the exploration of novel weed control methods further to enhance support for farmers in managing weeds effectively.

How would the following help with the uptake of alternative weed control methods?

FIGURE 35. HOW WOULD THE FOLLOWING HELP WITH THE UPTAKE OF ALTERNATIVE WEED CONTROL METHODS?

The surveys' findings (Figure 35) reveal that there is strong support for the increased availability of information through various channels such as the Internet, newspapers, leaflets, booklets, YouTube, and podcasts. This wider accessibility of information can raise awareness about alternative weed control methods, making it easier for farmers to access valuable knowledge and resources. Many farmers also recognize the value of consulting specialists or experienced farmers, as this personalized guidance and insights can encourage them to consider and adopt alternative methods. Additionally, recommendations from fellow farmers are deemed influential in promoting the adoption of alternative weed control methods.

Financial assistance in the form of grants for equipment purchases and subsidies is perceived as significant by a substantial number of farmers. Such support can alleviate the initial costs associated with adopting new methods, making these alternatives more attractive to farmers. Demonstration events of the methods of interest also received support, as they allow farmers to observe alternative methods in action, providing practical exposure and building confidence in trying new approaches. Conducting trials of alternative methods is considered essential by many farmers, as these trials provide concrete evidence of the methods' effectiveness, encouraging wider adoption.

While there are varying responses regarding the influence of public opinion and customer demands, some farmers recognize their potential impact on their decision-making. A positive shift in public perception toward greener weed control methods, including changes in food consumption habits, can create demand for sustainable practices, influencing farmers' choices. Similarly, customer preferences for products produced with reduced herbicide usage can incentivize farmers to adopt alternative methods. The influence of grants to establish trials for evaluating effectiveness is perceived as relatively less influential, providing such grants can contribute to the collection of valuable data and evidence supporting the effectiveness of alternative methods. On the other hand, there is strong disagreement regarding the introduction of stricter herbicide usage regulations as a factor in promoting alternative weed control methods, although some farmers are open to the possibility.

Overall, the focus group suggests that implementing strategies such as increasing information availability, providing financial support, promoting practical experiences, and addressing public perception are crucial for fostering the uptake of alternative weed control methods among farmers. The positive impact of trials and financial incentives for environmentally friendly practices can further encourage farmers to adopt these alternatives, and peer experiences and success stories can be influential in this process.

Greek Survey Overview

This survey unveils a spectrum of needs and barriers that play a pivotal role in influencing farmers' decisions to adopt alternative weed control methods in Greece. The focus group was invited to a session where the results were presented. Throughout the workshop, participants contributed mainly through discussion with note taking from AUA. Following the introduction, the workshop was split into two main parts; the current methods for alternative weed control and the barriers to uptake of alternative weed control and the solutions to increase uptake. Six needs and associated barriers were agreed, summarised below:

1. Access to Information and Concerns about Effectiveness:

- **Barrier:** Lack of information and awareness about alternative methods among farmers.
- **Barrier:** Limited availability of resources and educational materials.
- **Barrier:** Lack of opportunities for farmers to test alternative weed control methods before committing to significant investments.
- **Barrier:** Farmers' unfamiliarity with other farmers who have successfully adopted alternative methods, leading to uncertainty.
- **Barrier:** Farmers' concerns about the efficiency and effectiveness of alternative weed control methods, leading to uncertainty and reluctance to adopt

2. Skilled Advisors:

- **Barrier:** Absence of experts or consultants who can provide guidance on alternative weed control methods.

3. Demonstration and Trials:

- **Barrier:** Limited opportunities for farmers to observe alternative methods in action and gain practical exposure.
- **Barrier:** Lack of concrete evidence and data about the effectiveness of alternative methods.

4. Financial Support:

- **Barrier:** Perception of high costs associated with adopting new methods, including equipment and initial investment.
- **Barrier:** Affordability concerns for farmers, making alternative methods seem less viable.
- **Barrier:** Inadequate access to necessary equipment required for implementing alternative methods

5. Public Perception:

- **Barrier:** Lack of public awareness about the benefits and effectiveness of sustainable practices.

6. Peer Influence:

- **Barrier:** Lack of positive peer experiences and success stories that could encourage farmers to adopt alternative methods.

In addition to these barriers, some general barriers that cut across multiple needs include:

1. Negative Reviews:

- **Barrier:** Negative feedback and reviews from other farmers or sources can discourage farmers from trying alternative methods.

2. Regulatory Constraints:

- **Barrier:** Perception that regulations and guidelines limit the use of certain alternative weed control methods.

3. Time Constraints:

- **Barrier:** Farmers' concerns about the time-consuming nature of some alternative methods, which may not align with their operational schedules.

4. Environmental Considerations:

- **Barrier:** Uncertainty about the environmental impact of certain alternative methods, leading to hesitation in adoption.

Greek Summary

In Greece, conventional agriculture remains the predominant method of managing crops, and chemical removal, such as using herbicides, is the primary approach to dealing with weeds. This traditional farming system relies heavily on the use of synthetic chemicals to control weed populations and ensure optimal crop growth and yields. However, as concerns about environmental sustainability and the potential health impacts of chemical use have increased, there has been a growing interest in exploring alternative weed control methods that are more eco-friendly and promote long-term agricultural viability. Integrating sustainable practices and exploring diverse weed management strategies can help address the challenges posed by conventional agriculture and contribute to a more environmentally conscious and resilient agricultural sector in Greece. The outcomes of the survey reveal several barriers that impede the widespread adoption of alternative weed management techniques. These hindrances include the considerable costs associated with initiating and maintaining alternative methods, making them less feasible for financially constrained farmers. Additionally, the lack of opportunities to assess the effectiveness of these methods on specific crops and conditions leads to hesitation among farmers. Availability and affordability of necessary specialized equipment also act as a deterrent. Furthermore, inadequate awareness and understanding of alternative weed management practices, their benefits, and suitability for different farming systems contribute to the challenges. To address these obstacles comprehensively, a multifaceted approach involving governmental support, agricultural extension services, research institutions, and farmer associations is necessary. This approach should encompass financial incentives, demonstration events, information dissemination through workshops and online resources, and collaborative efforts among farmers, researchers, and advisors. By employing such strategies, effective and environmentally friendly weed management practices can be promoted in Greece.

3.5 Latvia results

Overview of Latvian farmer and associated stakeholder profiles

A total number of participants who completed the survey from Latvia 111. Farmers made up 82% of the participants, the remaining 18% were non-farmers and constituted of: 10% agricultural advisors, 10% industry representatives, 25% working for a governmental institution, 30% researchers (academic or other) and 15% selected 'other'. Of the non-farmers, 80% had direct contact with farmers as part of their professional responsibilities.

Half of the participants agreed with five statements relating to the usage of chemical herbicides and the potential negative impacts that their use can have on the user, the environment and any resistance management efforts in place. Forty one percent of all participating farmers disagreed or strongly disagreed with these statements as shown in Figure 36. Number of the farmers who disagree is three times bigger, than in UK. If we speak about non-farmers, then they are a little bit more critical to herbicide use – 22% of no-farmer respondents disagreed to above mentioned statements about the effects of the herbicide use.

FIGURE 36. PERCENTAGE RESPONSES OF FARMERS THAT PARTICIPATED IN THE ONLINE SURVEY RELATING TO FIVE STATEMENTS ON HERBICIDE USAGE AND THEIR IMPACTS ON THE USER, THE ENVIRONMENT AND THE DEVELOPMENT OF RESISTANT WEEDS.

Of the 91 participants that were farmers and completed the Latvia online survey, 85% indicated that cereals and oilseeds were the predominant crop type on their farm. Vegetable growers, vineyards, potatoes and sugar beet and other fruit or crops were also represented within the survey as shown in Figure 37.

FIGURE 37. PERCENTAGE OF FARMERS COMPLETING THE LATVIAN SURVEY AND THEIR SELECTION OF PREDOMINANT CROP TYPE (N=91).

When determining management styles of farming most farmers (58%) identified that they are following conventional approach. 33% of farmers identified that they followed an IPM or IWM approach. This is an interesting fact, because all the farmers should follow the IPM or IWM, what is defined by the law in Latvia. Maybe farmers still do not see the difference in this terminology. The smallest percentage of participants stated that they followed agroecological approach (1%) and conservation agricultural practices (2%) and the remaining 5% were organic. The size of farm managed by farmers completing the survey ranged from <5 to >1,000 ha and the median size of farm was within the size category 100.5-300 ha.

Herbicides were the most used weed control method identified, with 88% of farmers reliant on their application from the survey data. Other popular weed management approaches included cultivations (40%), cultural control (59%), mechanical weeding (55%) and hand weeding (15%). The main disadvantages to these approaches were:

- Negative public opinions (herbicides)
- Time consumption (mechanical weed control)
- Low efficacy
- Expense (mechanical weed control, camera guided mechanical weeding)
- Complicated methodology
- Harmful to the environment

Six participants left feedback on the camera guided hoes in the question about the used methods and their barriers, but only one has marked, that he is using it. According to our survey, camera guided hoes is one of the most popular method that farmers were interested in (20%).

A larger proportion (50/91) of participants had used mechanical weeders, and this method was also identified by many farmers as something they had wanted to use but have not done so yet (30%). More than 40% of participants were interested in targeted herbicides, and seven of all the participants had used these approaches previously for weed control on their farm. There was interest

in all alternative weed control approaches listed in Question 11 (Appendix 1) but, no farmers had previously used robotics, hot water/foam, flame weeding, lasers, or microwave weed control methods in Latvia. The reason given for this was no available equipment/product on local market, no previous demonstration in Latvian conditions, doubts about how complicated and time consuming these methods may be and concerns whether these methods have low efficacy.

When asked where participants got the latest news in agriculture, staying up to date on legislative changes, state support, events, grants etc., survey participants in the Latvia indicated that they used several sources of information, but the most popular sources of information were at events and seminars, demo days, via the internet and directly from consultants and advisors. These avenues should be explored by WP5 of OPER8 to maximise communication and dissemination to stakeholders in Latvia.

Latvian farmer needs, and associated barriers to, increasing uptake of alternative weed control solutions.

The Latvia focus group was held online to give more people the opportunity to attend at a busy time in the Latvian farming calendar. In preparation for the workshop an agenda was sent out to the Latvian stakeholders, online survey results were presented at the start of the meeting. In the focus group, the results of the survey were discussed with the NN to gain a deeper insight and contextual understanding behind the results. Thirteen people attended the focus group workshop, consisting of two arable farmers, one apple orchard farmer, three government policy workers, two lead researchers from LBTU, one representative for the Organic Farming association, one representative from the plant protection product association, one national network operator. The workshop began with a short introduction of all the participants and then an overview of the Oper8 project. Throughout the workshop, participants contributed mainly through discussion with note taking from LBTU. Following the introduction, the workshop was split into two main parts; the barriers to uptake of alternative weed control and the solutions to increase uptake. The needs and barriers of stakeholders to increase uptake of alternative weed control were discussed orally by giving word to each of the participant, there was an option to write the comments also in the chat. The needs for increased alternative weed control uptake in Latvia were split into five main categories and participants were asked to comment on each of these topics, and invited to identify any further barriers they were aware of. Five needs and associated barriers were agreed and are listed with comments from the NN summarized below:

The need: Farmers need greater confidence in the efficacy of alternative weed control methods.

This is relevant across all cropping systems and farm management styles across Latvia.

Barrier: There is a lack of transparent, scientifically based efficacy trials and demonstrations of the efficacy of alternative weed control methods.

Weed management efficacy, carbon release, and biodiversity impacts need to be rigorously assessed on a range of soil types. For example, there is a lack of quantitative data showing the effect of alternative approaches relative to conventional strategies in relation to weed control and profit margins. Some alternative weed methods include moving soil, such as mechanical inter row hoes, which is contradictory to best practice for reducing carbon release from soils¹².

There is no research made on ploughed vs minimal tillage system evaluation in terms of weed control. In Latvia minimal tillage systems become more popular and supported.

Barrier: There is a lack of funding available for high quality trials made by researchers or other independent companies.

In Latvia it is not very common practice to make independent trials, which are sponsored by farmer communities. Mostly these are by government or other kind of project sponsored trials.

Barrier: Results from alternative weed control trials are not easily accessible to farmers.

There is a need to set out some Living Labs or Light houses to spread out the experience to Farmers. At the moment there are some projects on alternative weed control. Networking opportunities are essential in which farmers can discuss research findings within established and trusted communities.

Barrier: There is a general lack of independent information on alternative weed control solutions, including the approaches available for different cropping systems as well as cost benefit analyses for each approach.

Barrier: In Latvia there are quite a small amount of information about alternative weed control. There are some trials led by researchers.

The need: Farmers need access to alternative weed control equipment.

Barrier: There is a lack of alternative weed control technology on the market, especially in Latvian arable production.

No electrical weeders are available and popularized on Latvian market. A few robots are coming to Latvia, but these are only individual case.

Barrier: There is a large initial investment need for the weeding equipment, the operational and labour costs will be also high. There are some doubts about efficiency also.

In Latvian horticulture, due to the higher revenue per hectare in comparison to arable production, alternative weed control uptake is generally greater than that for Latvian arable production. The high purchase price and running costs make some weed control approaches difficult to apply on a larger scale in arable production. There is a bigger potential to introduce the alternative methods in the horticulture sector also because of the unavailability of alternative weed control pesticides for organic farming.

Barrier: Latvians are not very keen on sharing equipment in a cooperative. There is quite a small window for usage of the alternative equipment (for example, mechanical weeder, camera guided hoe), therefore it is very difficult to share the equipment.

The need: Farmers need affordable alternative solutions for weed control.

Barrier: Specialist weed control equipment is expensive so it is difficult to justify its purchase and usage outside of high market value crops.

Barrier: Current grants for the purchase of alternative weed control equipment are competitive and are economically driven.

Stakeholders considered grants for the purchase of equipment to be useful for the uptake of alternative weed control. But, current equipment grants, firstly, are funded under competitive conditions and secondly, farmer decides where to invest money. Mostly equipment is chosen, taking into account economic viability, but as alternative weed control equipment has high running costs, then priorities are given to different kind of equipment. Widening the scope of uptake would enable more farmers to source grant funding for investment.

Barrier: Sources of funding for environmentally friendly farming incentives are limited.

Financial incentives would be the fastest way to increase uptake of alternative weed control methods but sources of funding are limited. The inclusion of 'reduced herbicide usage' payments into future ECOSchemes, or similar ongoing subsidies, could be used alongside with machinery grants to offset higher running costs.

The need: Farmers need alternative solutions that are more effective than herbicides and less time consuming to implement.

Barrier: Alternative weed control solutions are currently perceived as less effective than herbicides. The working width of most specific equipment is generally smaller than current spray booms and requires slower travel speeds therefore increasing time

for a single weeding operation. The lower efficacy per pass for some solutions results in more passes per crop to achieve similar levels of control to herbicides. For example, mechanical weed control needs more times of application, slower working speed than boom sprayer.

The need: Farmers need more information on alternative weed control solutions. They need to see these solutions on their farms in cooperation with scientifically based methodology and rating of its efficiency on different soils, in different fields/crops/weeds.

Latvian Summary

In Latvia, a reliance on chemical herbicides was identified by farmers participating in the survey. However, there was strong agreement that long-term use of chemical herbicides can have detrimental effects on the user, the environment and can lead to the development of resistance in weed populations. Farmers are interested in alternative methods of weed control but there are key barriers preventing their uptake relating to a lack of access to equipment and information, the high cost associated with alternative equipment and no opportunities to access alternatives or speak with others that have experience with an alternative approach. To increase uptake of alternative weed control in Latvia, stakeholders need a broad combination of tools to be implemented. There is a need for independent (researcher made) trials and demonstrations to increase knowledge and confidence in weed control solutions and for results to be disseminated effectively. Farmers need greater access to equipment through trusted networks, or by exploring the potential for grants and subsidies to increase uptake.

3.6 Sweden results

Overview of Swedish farmer and associated stakeholder profiles

In Sweden, a total of 51 participants completed the survey, and they all had their country of residence within Sweden. Farmers made up 53% of the participants, the remaining were non-farmers and constituted of 15% agricultural advisors, 10% working for a governmental institution, 10% researchers (academic or other) and 12% selected 'other'. Of the non-farmers, 92% had direct contact with farmers as part of their professional responsibilities. All participants had been working in the field of agriculture across a range of under 5 years to more than 20 years and 57% of all survey participants had been working in this field for more than 20 years.

Most participants agreed with five statements relating to the usage of chemical herbicides and the potential negative impacts that their use can have on the user, the environment and any resistance management efforts in place (Figure 38). More are convinced that herbicide have a negative impact on the environment and that weed resistance can increase compared with the effects on human health.

FIGURE 38. PERCENTAGE RESPONSES OF FARMERS THAT PARTICIPATED IN THE ONLINE SURVEY RELATING TO FIVE STATEMENTS ON HERBICIDE USAGE AND THEIR IMPACTS ON THE USER, THE ENVIRONMENT AND THE DEVELOPMENT OF RESISTANT WEEDS.

Of the 27 participants that were farmers and completed the Swedish online survey, 67% indicated that cereals and oilseeds were the predominant crop type on their farm. A few had indicated that their predominant crop was potatoes/sugar beets, while the rest indicated “other” crop. No one had marked that they produced wine, vegetables or fruit as these are not major outputs from Sweden.

When determining management styles of farmers, the management approaches were not defined within the survey, this led the participants to define and select the term they most identified with. It should also be emphasized that it is mandatory to use IPM to some extent, so this question is in this respect problematic. It depends to some extent on the farmer’s conscience if they state that they use IPM or not. However, just over half of the farmers (56%) stated that they followed an IPM or IWM approach, while 26% used conventional farming and the remaining 18% were organic. The size of farm managed by farmers completing the survey ranged from 10 to >1,000ha and the median size of farm was within the size category 100.5-300 ha.

The sum of different IPM-solutions was actually more commonly used weed management strategy than herbicides according to the farmer’s choices in the survey. Common IPM weed management approaches included cultural control (18%), cultivation (10%) and varietal choice (9%). The sum for these approaches were 37%. Still the individual most common strategy indicated was herbicides (23%) and mechanical weeding was also quite common (18%). Other strategies were less commonly used, the rest of the farmers (21%) indicated any of these and no strategy was indicated by more than 5% of the respondents.

The main disadvantages indicated were that the mechanical and the cultivation methods were considered too time consuming, and the mechanical method were also indicated as expensive.

Few participants had used camera guided hoes despite this being identified as the most common method that farmers were interested in (25%). Other Precision Agricultural techniques was also indicated as interesting for the participants to test such as robotics (18%), targeted herbicides (23%) and precision inter or intra row hoes (18%). Bioherbicides were indicated as interesting by 12 % of the participants while no other technique attracted more than 10% each.

It is thus clear that the more sophisticated camera assisted techniques seem to attract most attention. It may be that most already claim that they use IPM-methods and to make a significant step forwards, these techniques are the best option, although some also indicate that they are time consuming and that they are expensive.

The most important barriers indicated by the farmers for taking up alternative methods to a larger extent were primarily their low efficiency, that they are too expensive and that there are too few opportunities to test the methods before investing. Thus, it is not solely a problem with information about the methods, it is more that the methods efficiency and value for money need to be proven in practice (Figure 39).

FIGURE 39. BARRIERS TO UPTAKE OF ALTERNATIVE WEED CONTROL METHODS FOR FARMERS IN SWEDEN

Non-farmers had a different opinion in that they think that the lack of information about the alternative methods is the most important barrier and that they do not think that the price is so much of an issue. However, they agree with the farmers that the low efficacy of the methods is an important barrier.

Regarding solutions, the farmers think that the most important one is to make it more economically interesting to use the alternative methods, such as grants for purchase as was one of the proposed solutions in the survey (Figure 40). After that, different activities that increase knowledge transfer are also judged as important and among these positive examples are considered valuable. New regulations and public demands are not considered efficient.

Non-farmers agree that demonstrations and other knowledge transfer activities among other recommendations from other farmers are efficient measures. However, they believe that regulations and public demands are more important than the farmers and they do not think that grants for purchase of equipment are effective.

FIGURE 40. FARMERS VIEWS ON SOLUTIONS TO INCREASE UPTAKE OF ALTERNATIVE WEED CONTROL METHODS

Swedish farmer needs, and associated barriers to, increasing uptake of alternative weed control solutions. Focus group discussion.

The Swedish focus group was held online on the 17 August 2023. In preparation for the workshop an agenda and a summary of survey results (as presented above) was sent round to all the participants. In the focus group, the results of the survey were discussed with the NN to gain a deeper insight and contextual understanding behind the results. Sixteen people attended the focus group workshop, including Charlotta Wångdahl and Thomas Börjesson from Agroväst.

The Focus group consisted of six people from the Swedish Board of Agriculture, with different advisory and policy-making roles at this governmental authority. All have roles dealing with weeds and herbicides. Most are primarily working with field crops such as cereals and rape seed, while one of them is horticulture agronomist. One of them is secretary at the Swedish Plant Protection Council that have as their main task to introduce plant protection products with as low harmful effect on humans and the environment as possible and also to survey alternative methods for plant protection and another one of them is working with IPM implementations in Sweden. The County Administrative Board in West Sweden (Västra Götaland) was represented by one of their advisors who among other tasks is responsible for the education of farmers in spraying technology. One researcher who is a professor in weed biology at the Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences (SLU) attended. Two advisors from the largest farm advisory organisation in Sweden, Hushållningssällskapet, also took part. One of these is primarily working with cereals and the other one works primarily with horticultural crops. Two scientists working with technical development in this area from the largest Swedish research institute working in the agriculture sector, RISE, Research Institute of Sweden, also took part. One participant came from Nordic Beet Research contributed with inputs from the beet growers. We had also one member in the Focus Group from KEMI, Swedish Chemicals Agency, with responsibility of legislative issues. Last but not least, one member from the Swedish Crop Protection Organization also took part. They represent the company's manufacturing pesticides in Sweden. Thus, all attendants were very well connected to and familiar with the use of with herbicides, applications and the problem they cause. People with technical knowledge were also well represented. Farmer's perspective was however largely lacking, but one farmer who is also board member of the Swedish association of cereal growers was interviewed after the meeting, on the 18 August 2023.

The workshop began with a short introduction of all the participants, an overview of the Oper8 project and a summary of the results from the survey in Sweden. After that all attendants were asked, one by one, to shortly comment the survey results and then present their own thought on the most important needs and barriers for lowering the use of herbicides indicated in the Green Deal.

1. The need: Cropping systems in Sweden need to be more diverse to be able to reduce the use of herbicides. It is important to think more about what could be accepted in terms of weeds, not to get rid of all of them.

Barrier: A typical problem that is apparent in Sweden is that there are too few perennial crops in crop rotations and that in particular winter wheat is a very common crop. Fields and farms are increasing in size, which tends to make it more difficult to make farm-wise or field-wise adjustments that would be needed to handle local differences in weed densities and species distribution.

Possible solution: Reduced tillage and delayed sowing can be effective in reducing weeds without changing the crop rotations. Solutions that encourage perennial crops in areas with a lack of these crops today is also needed: This could be virtual fences to make it possible to move grazing animals more efficiently. Another solution can be to increase the demand for perennial crops such as grasses. This in turn can be achieved if projects that are running now on processing grasses into foods and feed will be successful. If less cereals are used as feeds at the same time, that would also have a possible influence on this. Promoting new crops that are more competitive against weeds, such as hemp, is also beneficial. It is also essential to find indicators for how to define a diverse cropping system. Work on this is going on within the Plant Protection Council.

Another way to go that was discussed is that it may be possible to confront farmers that actually do not use IPM solutions although these measured are compulsory. It was also noted that 26% of the farmers in the survey indicated that they ran the farm conventionally. To increase the demands on farmers to actually implement IPM-solutions could also be a way of actually improve the cropping systems. If there would be more consequences for the farmer if IPM is not used, the use would probably increase.

Certification systems that promote environmentally friendly production such as IP-suisse, (<https://www.ipsuisse.ch/>) was one solution that was mentioned.

2. The need: Technology such as row hoes are not used practically to a large extent.

Barrier: It is still not economically interesting enough to invest in such equipment, particularly not in cereals, where most of the herbicides are used today.

Possible solution: There should be subsidies for investing in for example row hoes. There is also a need for more demos and trials where the different methods can be compared in an objective manner. For hoes it may be important to demonstrate under which circumstances (soil types, weather) that they can be used efficiently.

3. The need: Focus on the “right” herbicides that are dominant and that causes most of the problems. In Sweden seven substances constitute 60% of the herbicide use.

Possible solution: Since the goal is specifically to reduce the use of herbicides, it would be wise to primarily concentrate on solutions that specifically reduce the use of these. For instance, there are detailed plans on how to handle a situation without glyphosate, which is the most used herbicide in Sweden. This could either be done by changing cropping systems or by use of different technologies such as spot-spraying.

4. The need: The less sophisticated solutions such as adjustment of sprayers, choice of the right nozzles etc. could also lead to substantial reduction of the use. It also essential to get different components to work together in a more efficient manner. When it comes to spraying technology, we have seen much less progress in terms of Precision Agriculture compared with fertilizing. It is essential to not only emphasize on new technology, since technology is only replaced very slowly. For instance, in Sweden, 150 new sprayers are sold each year, whereas about 6000 sprayers are in use regularly.

Barrier: One important barrier is that when testing sprayers, it is not enough emphasis on the actual amount of herbicides used, more focus is on driftage, if the herbicides are not reaching their target. It is difficult to make equipment from different manufacturers to communicate.

Possible solutions: A supplementation of the requirements when testing sprayers, that the amount of herbicides used is more in focus. The use of improved technology should be encouraged, maybe with subsidies. Examples of such technologies are pulse width modulation (PWM) nozzles and camera assisted systems (e.g. DAT EcoPatch) that can be used on existing sprayers could possibly save more herbicides than solutions that require more investments. It is also beneficial with systems that facilitates communication between different systems such as ISOBUS.

5. The need: Uptake of new technology such as drones to establish weed management zones or robots. One aspect that is important is that in many crops there is a lack of staff, so that the manual work actually needs to be replaced.

Barrier: The methods are still in general not flexible enough. For a farmer the most important thing is to have the weed management done at exactly the right development stage of the crop and the weeds and that can still be difficult to achieve using these technologies. Considering drones, it could be a problem if the service is provided by an entrepreneur and that the service may not be available exactly when it is needed.

Barrier: There are at least among most farmers a certain reluctance against changing concepts, in particular if you are unfamiliar with the new concepts. In Sweden, the age of the average farmer is also quite high.

Possible solutions: One solution that was discussed and that some entrepreneurs also employ, is to guarantee a certain effect and that the farmer do not need to care about how the task is fulfilled. An example could be a guarantee that the use of herbicides is reduced and at the same time there should not be a substantial yield loss. Another solution could be that the service is well incorporated in the “normal” advisory service, so that for instance a drone flight is integrated in a visit by an advisor.

Also, regarding these technologies, demos and compensations for investments could be suitable ways forward.

6. Need: From a resistance point of view, it is better to avoid one spraying occasion instead of lowering the dose. In horticultural crops and sugar beets in Sweden, there is a high demand on keeping the crops free from weeds, and the use of herbicides are often combined with mechanical solutions.

Barrier: Today most farmers are primarily dependant on herbicides for weed management. The mechanical technology that is used today, have often too low capacity for the larger farms. An example is Farmdroid that is common on primarily smaller farms.

Possible solutions: About half of the beet growers in Sweden use mechanical weed control to some extent, so farmers are interested and the technology is often in place at the farm. One way forward is to use more efficient technology, so that the job can be done quicker, possibly using larger technology to cover more rows or robots that are slow but in service continuously. The economical aspect is also important: One solution could be to have some kind of further developed IPM-concept that is something between organic and conventional production. Systems that allow mineral fertilizers but not pesticides were discussed.

Sweden Summary

It was quite clear from the discussion, that it should be possible to move towards a lowering of the use of herbicides and that the Swedish farmers have already decreased the use quite substantially already. However, the use of herbicides has actually increased somewhat lately due partly to the increased acreage of winter wheat during the past few years.

A change in cropping system was discussed by quite a few of the participants and how that can be combined with an increased focus on IPM-solutions is probably an important way forward.

An interesting discussion was also on how to target the decrease in herbicide use: What is the key problem? Is it loss in resistance, leakage or health aspects? That could influence which components to focus on. According to the survey, it seems that in Sweden, the environmental issues are dominant.

It was also obvious that most agreed on that the farmer's economy should be in focus. In order to decrease the use of herbicides, farmers need to be compensated somehow. It could be with a new concept with a higher price for crops than in a conventional system, but it could also be some kind of compensation for investments in new technology.

Many also pointed out that most farmers are reluctant to invest in a totally new technology and that success may come faster if systems that are already in use can be upgraded such as introduction of more efficient spraying nozzles and cameras attached to existing sprayers.

A general comment is also that robots may have a bright future since it is difficult to get staff for manual work. The introduction of new technology may also attract employees.

3.7 Spain results

Overview of Spain farmer and associated stakeholder profiles

In Spain, a survey was performed with a participation from a total of 80 individuals. Among these respondents, 79 indicated Spain as their country of residence, while one participant was presently situated in the United Kingdom. Of the participants, 39% identified as farmers, with the remaining 61% categorized as non-farmers. This non-farmer segment encompassed diverse roles: 31% as agricultural advisors, 8% employed within governmental institutions, 6% as industry representatives, 39% as researchers (across academic or other domains), and 16% self-designated as 'other'. Among the non-farmers, an impressive 76% affirmed direct engagement with farmers as an integral aspect of their professional obligations. Collectively, the participants boasted an array of

experience in the agricultural domain, spanning from less than 5 years to upwards of 20 years. Remarkably, almost half of the survey respondents (49%) could boast over two decades of experience within this field.

The consensus among the majority of participants was aligned with five specific statements concerning the utilization of chemical herbicides and the plausible adverse ramifications these substances could impact upon the operator, the surrounding ecosystem, and the efficacy of resistance management strategies currently enacted. A segment comprising roughly ten percent of the entire cohort of participating farmers expressed dissent, either through disagreement or strong disagreement, with respect to these articulated propositions, as visually represented in Figure 41.

FIGURE 41. PERCENTAGE RESPONSES OF FARMERS THAT PARTICIPATED IN THE ONLINE SURVEY RELATING TO FIVE STATEMENTS ON HERBICIDE USAGE AND THEIR IMPACTS ON THE USER, THE ENVIRONMENT AND THE DEVELOPMENT OF RESISTANT WEEDS.

Among the 31 participants who identified themselves as farmers a discernible pattern emerged. Specifically, 29% of these participants disclosed vineyards as the prevailing crop type on their farms, while an additional 22% highlighted cereals and oilseeds as the dominant agricultural products cultivated on their holdings. Furthermore, the survey encompassed a spectrum of agricultural endeavours, encompassing vegetable cultivation, vineyards, potato farming, and sugar beet cultivation. In addition, the "Other crops" classification garnered significant attention, constituting a substantial 39% of the farmers who actively participated in the survey, as visually represented in Figure 42.

FIGURE 42. PERCENTAGE OF FARMERS COMPLETING THE SPANISH SURVEY AND THEIR SELECTION OF PREDOMINANT CROP TYPE (N=44).

During the evaluation of farmers' management styles, the survey refrained from imposing pre-defined categorizations on management approaches. Out of all the farmers who took part, the biggest group (32%) said they use a Conventional farming approach. The next popular methods were Organic farming (26%) and IPM/IWM at 19%. A smaller number of farmers said they followed regenerative farming (10%), agroecological practices (7%), or conservation farming (3%), with 3% 'other'. The farms that

the surveyed farmers managed came in various sizes, ranging from less than 5 hectares to over 1,000 hectares. The typical farm size, or median, was between 30.1 and 100 hectares.

Herbicides were the most used weed control method identified, with 38% of farmers reliant on their application from the survey data. Other popular weed management approaches included cultivations (29%), hand weeding (32%), mechanical weeding (22%) and mowing (29%). The main disadvantages to these approaches were.

- Expenses
- Time consumption
- Complicated methodology
- High carbon footprint
- Harmful to the environment

Not a lot of participants had used selective herbicides (0/31), mechanical weeding (7/31), agricultural practices (5/31), varieties selection (16/31) and camera guided hoes (0/31) despite these being identified as the most common methods that farmers were interested in with over 75% for mechanical weeding and selective herbicides, 67% for camera guided hoes, 58% for agricultural practices and 51% for varieties selection. A notable segment (12 out of 44) of the participants reported utilizing herbicides. Furthermore, a significant subset of farmers expressed their inclination towards using herbicides, although they had yet to do so (38%). It is of particular significance to reiterate that over 67% of the participants exhibited interest in adopting camera-guided hoes, yet none had employed this methodology previously for weed management on their agricultural holdings.

In recapitulation, a keen interest was demonstrated across all enumerated alternative weed control methodologies, as outlined in Question 11 (refer to Appendix 1.). However, among the surveyed farmers in Spain, there was a lack of prior engagement with methods such as robotics, precision hoes, allelopathy, selective herbicides, variety selection, bioherbicides, hot water/foam applications, and microwave-based weed control. The primary rationales cited for this absence were centred around the substantial cost of requisite equipment and the perceived complexity and time-intensive nature of these methodologies.

When asked where participants got the latest news in agriculture, staying up to date on legislative changes, state support, events, grants etc., survey participants in Spain indicated that they used several sources of information, but the most popular sources of information were social networks, friends, and close people, at events and seminars, through newspapers and magazines, via the internet and directly from consultants and advisors.

Spain farmer needs, and associated barriers to, increasing uptake of alternative weed control solutions.

The Spanish focus group (FG) meeting was held online (Figure 43) to facilitate people to attend considering the multiple meetings and tasks each professional had to participate on 28 July 2023. A PowerPoint presentation was prepared previous to the meeting to guide the discussion and aim to obtain the expected outcomes considering FG expertise. In the focus group, the results of the survey were displayed with the NN to gain a deeper insight and contextual understanding behind the results. Thirteen people attended the focus group workshop plus three from the organisation team, consisting of: three USC researchers acting as organizers plus one USC professor acting as expert and link with the FG participants, six farmers/agricultural farming companies' representatives, two industry participants, one representative acting as advisor with an administration background and three other advisors.

FIGURE 43. SCREENSHOT OF THE ONLINE SPANISH FG MEETING

The workshop began with a short introduction of all the participants and then an overview of the Oper8 project. Throughout the workshop, participants contributed mainly through discussion with note taking from the USC. Following the introduction, the workshop was split into two main parts; one of presenting the results and main conclusions with the survey participants categorization and contextualization, survey respondents' thoughts about current and future trends/activities within the weeding techniques and technologies and, finally the barriers to uptake of alternative weed control and the solutions to increase uptake (both including separated farmers/non farmers results).

A second part of the presentation included the guidelines to dynamize the discussion to get the FG input to the survey outcomes. The inputs and comments from the FG participants are the following:

Weed control methods

The meeting participants engaged in a discussion centred around advanced weeding techniques within crops. It was unanimously agreed that maintaining effective control over weeds is a historical cornerstone of successful agriculture. The conversation unveiled the widespread, albeit often unnoticed, utilization of allelopathy as a weeding strategy. Another participant concurred and expanded on the topic, citing the utilization of mechanical weeding in larger fields and the intriguing potential of camera-assisted tools. Practices like mulching with wood chips and herbs in horticulture were highlighted, along with the integration of silvopastoral methods for holistic pest and weed management, even involving poultry in orchards. The suggestion to delay wheat cultivation to minimize weed competition was introduced, along with the application of silvopasture for controlling herbaceous plants and pests damaging apples. Another perspective introduced the concept of incorporating livestock as an integral weed control component. The idea of deploying specific plant species to counter robust weeds was presented, often relying on mechanical approaches with intermittent herbicide use. The point was stressed that more resilient species demand additional mechanical attention, aligning with the broader notion of crop management. The discussion also pointed out the central challenge of managing under-crop line vegetation in various types of agricultural settings. The meeting participants effectively highlighted diverse weeding techniques, blending traditional and innovative methods.

Main problems on weed control methods

It was considered positive and correct that the survey results indicated that most problems for reduce alternative weed control uptake are related to being expensive, time-consuming, requiring expertise and heavy workload. It was also clearly stated that herbicides are harmful for the environment.

Barriers to uptake of alternative weed control

During the meeting, participants engaged in a comprehensive discussion on the challenges hindering the adoption of alternative weed control methods. It was acknowledged that the historical ease of herbicide utilization and its promotion posed a significant obstacle. The consensus emerged that insufficient training and guidance exacerbate the issue, while highlighting the crucial role of crop rotation as a remedy. The discourse also touched upon the conventional management of crops, emphasizing the need for a paradigm shift. Furthermore, the discourse underscored the importance of initiatives such as Oper8 in identifying barriers and providing real-time, accessible training through online platforms. The participants universally emphasized the necessity of advisor involvement in addressing this predicament. In exploring alternative approaches, the conversation revealed various insights. The lack of collaboration among farmers for shared investments in machinery emerged as a notable challenge. Advisors were consistently identified as pivotal elements, ensuring informed decision-making. Additionally, in the context of perennial crops, advisors were deemed vital, especially in viticulture, almond, and pistachio cultivation, given the difficulty of pre-investment experimentation. Concerns were raised regarding the limitations of trials conducted by private enterprises, which often yield biased results influenced by short-term interests. Highlighting a potential solution, the dissemination of successful case studies was proposed as a rapid and practical method for knowledge-sharing. The overall sentiment echoed that while solutions exist, the dissemination of experiences remains a critical factor that requires collective attention.

Main needs highlighted:

Need: Farmers require incentives to sow more perennial crops

Barrier: lack of information or incentive to do this currently.

Need: lack of confidence in alternative weed control methods as farmers would prefer to learn from other farmers that are using methods successfully.

Barriers:

- Lack of farmers sharing of kit
- Lack of information available on non-conventional cropping methods so people stick to 'what they know' and do not explore new options.

Need: More training/guidance and sharing of practical experience required on alternative methods.

Solutions to uptake of alternative weed control

The meeting participants discussed strategies to promote the adoption of alternative weed control methods. One participant was surprised by survey results that showed information availability was not as crucial as assumed. They suggested incentivizing non-herbicide use over penalties. Another noted the challenge of finding reliable information online and proposed sharing success stories while revitalizing regional agricultural extension offices for training. The importance of disseminating both existing knowledge and new experiments was highlighted. Additionally, utilizing agricultural training centres and shared machinery spaces for promotion was recommended. Overall, the discussions emphasized improving information dissemination, strengthening extension services, and utilizing existing agricultural resources to encourage alternative weed control practices.

Summary of the Spain Focus Group meeting

In conclusion, the discussion highlights several key aspects in the realm of agricultural practices in Spain. Control methods are integral, and the identification of effective techniques stands paramount. Incorporating animal utilization and emphasizing rotation practices emerge as critical considerations for comprehensive approaches. However, obstacles such as inadequate dissemination of knowledge and the erosion of traditional wisdom underscore the need for urgent action. The encroachment of corporate entities in the agricultural sector, focusing on a specific market segment, further complicates the landscape. To address these challenges, the establishment of advisory networks and fostering collaborative associations becomes imperative.

By harnessing collective expertise and traditional wisdom, a more sustainable and informed path forward can be charted for the agricultural domain.

Spain Summary

The study conducted in Spain aimed to assess the perspectives of farmers and stakeholders regarding weed control methods in agriculture. A comprehensive survey involved 80 participants, mostly from Spain, with 39% identifying as farmers and 61% as non-farmers. The non-farmer group included agricultural advisors, governmental employees, industry representatives, researchers, and others.

Most participants had substantial experience in agriculture, spanning from under 5 to over 20 years. While the majority agreed with statements on the potential drawbacks of chemical herbicides, around 10% of farmers dissented. Vineyards and cereals/oilseeds were dominant crops among the farmers, but a variety of agricultural endeavours were represented.

Different farming approaches were reported, with conventional farming (32%), organic farming (26%), and IPM/IWM (19%) being the most common. Herbicides were the primary weed control method (38%), followed by cultivations, hand weeding, mechanical weeding, and mowing. Despite interest, few participants had used or adopted alternative methods like selective herbicides, mechanical weeding, or camera-guided hoes. Cost and complexity were cited as barriers to these methods. Farmers gathered information from social networks, friends, events, newspapers, magazines, the internet, and advisors. A focus group meeting was held online, involving 13 participants along with organizers and experts. Participants discussed weed control methods, highlighting allelopathy, mechanical weeding, camera-assisted tools, and other innovative techniques. Challenges like expense, time consumption, and environmental harm associated with current methods were acknowledged.

Barriers to adopting alternative weed control were debated, including historical reliance on herbicides, lack of training, and resistance to change. Advisors and shared investments were seen as important for overcoming these barriers. Solutions discussed included incentivizing non-herbicide use, sharing success stories, revitalizing agricultural extension offices, and promoting collaborative associations.

In summary, the study underscored the need for effective weed control in agriculture. It emphasized incorporating animals and rotation practices, overcoming barriers through knowledge dissemination and collaboration, and addressing challenges posed by corporate interests. The study aimed to pave a sustainable path forward for agriculture through collective expertise and traditional wisdom.

Part. 4 Summary and Conclusions

The success of OPER8 hinges upon a thorough understanding of the specific needs and barriers faced by stakeholders. Through the comprehensive survey and collaborative focus group workshops, invaluable insights have been gained that will guide the next step within the project. By tailoring solutions to address the identified challenges, the project aims to ensure the effective adoption of sustainable weed control practices across diverse European regions.

From the survey responses and region- specific discussions conducted within focus group workshops, a clear consensus emerged regarding the desire to transition towards alternative methods due to concerns about environmental impact, sustainability, and long-term agricultural viability. Simultaneously, barriers such as economic constraints, technical uncertainties, and a lack of awareness were articulated, underlining the complex landscape within which solutions must be crafted.

4.1 Next steps within OPER8

Building on these localised insights, each region will craft a tailored national action plan (T2.4 & D2.4) that outlines the specific measures required to overcome identified barriers by matching the needs of stakeholders to the technical solutions identified by T2.3. These action plans will harmonise regional objectives with the broader project goals to facilitate the increased uptake of alternative weed control.

Appendix 1. Online survey questions; needs & barriers for alternative weed control.

2.

Which country do you live in?

- France
- Greece
- Italy Latvia
- Spain
- Sweden
- UK
- Other

2.a. If you selected Other, please specify:

3. Do you see yourself as a farmer or non-farmer?

- Farmer Non-
- farmer

Characteristics of the farm

4. **How many ha of agricultural land do you manage/own?**

- up to 5ha
- 5.1 to 10ha
- 10.1 to 30ha
- 30.1 to 100ha
- 100.1 to 300ha
- 300.1 - 500ha
- 500.1 - 1000ha
- over 1000ha

5. **Which is the predominant crop type on your farm (please tick one option)?**

If you manage several crops, please indicate the type providing the highest revenue.

- 1) Cereals/oilseeds
- 2) Potatoes and sugar beet
- 3) Vegetables
- 4) Vineyards
- 5) Other fruit
- 6) Other crops

5.a. If you selected 'other crops', please type your answer below.

6. **How would you describe your weed management?**

Note: Here, 'chemical' does not refer to the usage of bio-herbicides

- 1) Organic (no chemical inputs)
- 2) Integrated pest/weed management (IPM/IWM)
- 3) Conventional (reliant on chemical herbicides)

- 4) Conservation agriculture
- 5) Regenerative agriculture
- 6) Agroecological
- 7) Other

6.a. If you selected 'other', please type your answer below.

Current weed control problems / farmers

7. Which weed control methods are you currently using (multiple options possible)? Please indicate methods that you are using and select or specify one main disadvantage (if any) of the approach.

	Select	Main disadvantage	If you selected 'other', please specify in the box
herbicides	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select	
mechanical	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select	
camera guided inter- row or intra- row hoes	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select	
cultivations	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select	
cultural control (delayed drilling, rotations, cover crops, cultivar choice, high seed rates)	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select	
mowing	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select	
weeding by hand	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select	
mulches (membranes, organic)/living mulches	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select	
varietal choice	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select	

flame weeding/ precision inter or intra-row hoes/electrical	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select	
hot water or foam	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select	
robotic	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select	
microwave	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select	
bio-herbicides	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select	
laser	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select	
allelopathy	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select	
targeted herbicide application (e.g. see and spray)	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select	
other method 1	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select	
other method 2	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select	
other method 3	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select	

Key for selection options

Main disadvantage

- 1) No significant disadvantages
- 2) time-consuming
- 3) complicated
- 4) expensive
- 5) Low efficacy
- 6) harmful to the environment and human
- 7) high carbon footprint
- 8) public have a negative opinion towards the use of the method(s)
- 9) Customers demand the reduced use of the method(s)

Current weed control problems / farmers (2)

8. What is your opinion on the following statements relating to weed control methods currently used on your farm?

Please don't select more than 1 answer(s) per row.

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly agree
1) no significant disadvantages	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2) time-consuming	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3) complicated	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4) expensive	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5) low efficacy	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6) harmful to the environment and human	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
7) high carbon footprint	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
8) public have a negative opinion towards the use of the method(s)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
9) customers demand the reduced use of the method(s)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

9. What specific weed types are not addressed by your current weed control methods? (Multiple choices available)

- Annual grass weeds
- Annual broad-leaved weeds
- Perennial grasses
- Perennial broad leaved weeds
- Other

9.a. If you selected 'other', please type your answer below.

Current weed control problems- farmers (4)

10. What is your opinion on the effects of herbicides on humans and the environment?

Please don't select more than 1 answer(s) per row.

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly agree
1) Long-term use of the same herbicide in the same field can cause weeds to develop resistance	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2) Herbicides and residues can accumulate in environment and have negative effects on organisms	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3) Herbicides or their residues can enter the human body through food	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4) Herbicides contribute to the degradation of biodiversity	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5) Certain herbicides or their residues have carcinogenic properties	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Alternative weed control methods /farmers

11. Are there weed control methods that you are aware of and interested in, but have never used (multiple options possible)? Please indicate methods that you are interested in and select or specify one barrier describing why you have not tried this approach.

	Select	Main barrier
mechanical	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select
camera guided inter- row or intra-row hoes	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select
cultivations/cultural control (delayed drilling, rotations, cover crops, cultivar choice, high seed rates)	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select
herbicides	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select
mowing	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select
weeding by hand	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select
mulches (membranes, organic)/living mulches	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select
varietal choice	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select
flame weeding	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select
precision inter or intra- row hoes	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select
electrical /hot water or foam	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select
robotic	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select
microwave	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select
bio-herbicides	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select
laser	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select
allelopathy	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select
targeted herbicide application (e.g. see and spray)	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select
other method	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select

11.a. If 'other method' is selected, please specify in the box below

Key for selection options

Main disadvantage

- 10) No significant disadvantages
- 11) time-consuming
- 12) complicated
- 13) expensive
- 14) Low efficacy
- 15) harmful to the environment and human
- 16) high carbon footprint
- 17) public have a negative opinion towards the use of the method(s)
- 18) Customers demand the reduced use of the method(s)

Are there weed control methods that you have tried in the past, that you are no longer using?

Please indicate methods that you have used and select or specify one main disadvantage describing why you no longer use this approach.

12.	Used	Main disadvantage	Why no longer use it
mechanical	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select	
camera guided inter- row or intra- row hoes	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select	
cultivations	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select	
cultural control (delayed drilling, rotations, cover crops, cultivar choice, high seed rates)	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select	
mowing	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select	
weeding by hand	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select	
mulches (membranes, organic)/living mulches	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select	
varietal choice	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select	
flame weeding	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select	
precision inter or intra-row hoes	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select	
electrical	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select	
hot water or foam	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select	

robotic	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select	
microwave	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select	
bio- herbicides	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select	
laser	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select	
allelopathy	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select	
targeted herbicide application (e.g. see and spray)	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select	
other method	<input type="checkbox"/>	Please select	

12.a. If 'other method' is selected, please specify in the box below

Key for selection options

Main disadvantage

- 1) No significant disadvantages
- 2) time-consuming
- 3) complicated
- 4) expensive
- 5) Low efficacy
- 6) harmful to the environment and human
- 7) high carbon footprint
- 8) public have a negative opinion towards the use of the method(s)
- 9) Customers demand the reduced use of the method(s)

Alternative weed control methods / farmers (4)

13. How far do you agree with the following statements describing why farmers do not increase their use of alternative weed control methods?

Please don't select more than 1 answer(s) per row.

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly agree
There is a lack of information available about alternative weed control methods	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
No skilled advisors available	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Alternative weed control methods have low efficiency	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I do not have access to the required equipment	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I have heard negative reviews about alternative weed control methods	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
There are no opportunities to test alternative weed control method(s) before investing	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
The solutions are too expensive	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Regulations do not allow the use of the particular method	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
The method is time consuming	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Negative effect on biodiversity	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I do not know anyone that uses them	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Other reason	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

13.a. If you selected 'other reason', please specify.

14. In your opinion, how useful would the following scenarios be in order to increase the uptake of alternative weed control methods?

Please don't select more than 1 answer(s) per row.

	Not useful	Slightly useful	Somewhat useful	Very useful	Extremely useful
Increased availability of information (Internet, newspapers, leaflets, booklets, Youtube, podcasts, etc.)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Consultations with a specialist or experienced user	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Recommendations from other farmers	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Grants for the purchase of equipment	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Subsidies for environmentally friendly farming	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Demonstration events of the methods of interest	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Trials of alternative weed control methods	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Change of public opinion in favor of "greener" weed control methods (including food consumption habits)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Customer demands of reduced herbicide input	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Grants to establish trials to evaluate the effectiveness	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Introduction of stricter herbicide usage regulations	<input type="checkbox"/>				

Other circumstances

14.a. If 'other' selected, please specify other circumstances that would promote the use of alternative weed control methods.

15. What is your main occupation?

- Agricultural advisor Researcher
- (academic or other)
- Governmental institution (not directly related to policy)
- Politician (regional or national agricultural policy maker)
- Industry representative (agricultural machinery, raw materials, equipment and service) Other

16. Do your professional responsibilities include direct contact with farmers?

- Yes No
-

17. How do you perceive your contact with farmers?

Please don't select more than 1 answer(s) per row.

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly agree	N/A or don't know
1) Farmers ask for your advice or consultation on weed control issues	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2) Farmers follow your recommendations	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3) Farmers are satisfied with their current weed control methods	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4) Farmers are interested in novel weed control methods	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5) There is a shortage of information about alternative weed control methods for farmers	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Current weed control problems / non-farmers

18. Overall, what is your opinion on the following statements relating to **alternative** weed control methods used by farmers? (For example, tillage, mechanical weeding, robotics cultural control, delayed drilling, rotations, cultivar choice, high seed rates, false seedbeds, mowing, weeding by hand, precision application, bio-herbicides, etc.)

Please don't select more than 1 answer(s) per row.

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly agree	N/A or don't know
1) no significant disadvantages	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2) time-consuming	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3) complicated	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4) expensive	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5) low efficacy	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6) harmful to the environment and human	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
7) high carbon footprint	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
8) public have a negative opinion towards the use of the method(s)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
9) customers demand the reduced use of the method(s)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Herbicide-based weed control methods

19. Overall, what is your opinion on the following statements relating to **herbicide-based** weed control methods used by farmers?

Please don't select more than 1 answer(s) per row.

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly agree	N/A or don't know
1) no significant disadvantages	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2) time-consuming	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3) complicated	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4) expensive	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5) low efficacy	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6) harmful to the environment and human	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
7) high carbon footprint	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
8) public have a negative towards the use of the method(s)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
9) customers demand the reduced use of the method(s)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Impact of herbicides

20. What is your opinion on the effects of herbicides on humans and the environment?

Please don't select more than 1 answer(s) per row.

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly agree	N/A or don't know
1) Long-term use of the same herbicide in the same field can cause weeds to develop resistance	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2) Herbicides and residues can accumulate in environment and have negative effects on organisms	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3) Herbicides or their residues can enter the human body through food	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4) Herbicides contribute to the degradation of biodiversity	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5) Certain herbicides or their residues have carcinogenic properties	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Alternative methods of weed control/ non-farmers

21. How far do you agree with the following statements describing why farmers do not increase their use of alternative weed control methods?

Please don't select more than 1 answer(s) per row.

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree	N/A or don't know
There is a lack of information available about alternative weed control methods	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
No skilled advisors available	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Alternative weed control methods have low efficiency	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I do not have access to the required equipment	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I have heard negative reviews about alternative weed control methods	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
There are no opportunities to test alternative weed control method(s) before investing	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
The solutions are too expensive	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Regulations do not allow the use of the particular method	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
The method is time consuming	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Negative effect on biodiversity	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I do not know anyone that uses them	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Other reason	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

21.a. If you selected 'other', please type your answer below.

Alternative weed control/ non-farmers (2)

22. In your opinion, how useful would the following scenarios be in order to increase the uptake of alternative weed control methods?

Please don't select more than 1 answer(s) per row.

	Not useful	Slightly useful	Somewhat useful	Very useful	Extremely useful	N/A or don't know
Increased availability of information (Internet, newspapers, leaflets, booklets, YouTube, podcasts, etc.)	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Consultations with a specialist or experienced user	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Recommendations from other farmers	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Grants for the purchase of equipment	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Subsidies for environmentally friendly farming	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Demonstration events of the methods of interest	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Trials of alternative weed control methods	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Change of public opinion in favor of "greener" weed control methods (including food consumption habits)	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Customer demands of reduced herbicide input	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Grants to establish trials to evaluate the effectiveness	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Introduction of stricter herbicide usage regulations	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Other circumstances	<input type="checkbox"/>					

22.a. If 'other' selected, please specify other circumstances that would promote the use of alternative weed control methods

5. General questions

23. What is your age group?

- 20 or under
- 21-30
- 31-40
- 41-50
- 51-60
- 61 or over

24. What is the highest level of education you have attained

- Vocational qualification (Including BTEC, NVQ, OCR)
- Bachelor's degree
- Master's degree
- PhD
- Other

24.a. If you selected 'other', please type your answer below.

25. Do you have a specialised education in the field of agriculture? (please tick all that apply)

- No
- Vocational qualification with specialisation in agriculture
- Higher education with specialisation in agriculture
- Continuous professional development courses (CPD) Other
- formal qualification

25.a. If you selected 'other', please type your answer below.

General questions (2)

26. How long have you been working in the field of agriculture?

- up to 5 years
- 5-10 years
- 10-20 years
- over 20 years N/A
- or don't know

27. Where do you get the latest news in agriculture (for example, about legislative changes, state support, grant programs, etc.)? (please tick all that apply)

- Social media
- From friends, acquaintances and colleagues
- Newspapers and magazines
- TV
- Radio
- Internet
- Seminars and events
- Consultants and advisors
- Direct contact with governmental representatives
- industry representatives
- Other

27.a. If you selected 'other', please type your answer below.

28. Are you a member of any non-governmental agricultural related organisations?

- No
- Trade union Farmer
- cooperative
- Horizontal non-governmental organisation (farmer to farmer) Professional
- non-governmental organisation (e.g farming unions) Other
- Don't Know

